

Master thesis in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Improving Generalization of Deep Learning Music Classifiers

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Context and Motivation	1
1.2	Challenges	2
1.3	Research Questions	6
1.4	Contributions	8
2	Related Work	10
2.1	Outliers Detection in Audio Data	10
2.1.1	Problem Definition	10
2.1.2	Geometrical Methods	11
2.1.3	Statistical Methods	12
2.1.4	Overview	12
2.2	Audio Data Augmentation	13
2.2.1	Problem Definition	13
2.2.2	Existing Methods	14
2.3	Label Smoothing	15
2.3.1	Formulation	15
2.3.2	Audio-Related Applications	16
2.3.3	Motivations	16
2.4	Loss Functions	17
2.4.1	Problem Definition	17
2.4.2	Existing Approaches	18

2.5	Multi-Task Learning	19
2.5.1	Problem Definition	19
2.5.2	Application to Audio Data	20
2.5.3	Disjoint Datasets	21
3	Experimental Setting	23
3.1	Tasks Addressed & Datasets	23
3.2	Deep Learning Models	24
3.2.1	Architectures	24
3.2.2	Training Strategies	25
3.2.3	Evaluation Process	26
3.3	Methodology	27
3.3.1	Training Procedure	27
3.3.2	Evaluation Procedure	27
4	Data Processing	28
4.1	Audio Outliers Detection	28
4.1.1	MP-Reject	28
4.1.2	Local Outlier Factor	30
4.1.3	Multi-Class Version	31
4.1.4	Subjective Evaluation	32
4.1.5	Conclusion	37
4.2	Audio Data Augmentation	38
4.2.1	Data Representation	38
4.2.2	Time-Swapping	38
4.2.3	Frequency-Masking	39
4.2.4	Loudness Control	39
4.2.5	Random Noise	40
4.2.6	Augmentation Policy	43

4.2.7	Results	45
4.2.8	Conclusion	46
5	Noise Robustness	48
5.1	Label Smoothing	48
5.1.1	Uniform Smoothing	49
5.1.2	Label Distribution Learning	50
5.1.3	Local Smoothing	54
5.1.4	Weighted Smoothing	56
5.1.5	Semantic-Aware Smoothing	59
5.1.6	Conclusion	68
5.2	Loss Functions	70
5.2.1	Bootstrapping	71
5.2.2	Generalized Cross-Entropy	73
5.2.3	Outlier-Aware Cross-Entropy	76
5.2.4	Conclusion	77
6	Knowledge Transfer	79
6.1	Multi-Task Learning	80
6.1.1	Disjoint Multi-Task Learning	81
6.1.2	Results	82
6.1.3	Two-Step Training	84
6.2	Further Transfer	85
6.2.1	Semi-Supervised Learning	85
6.2.2	Task Similarities	86
6.2.3	Meta-Learning	87
6.3	Conclusion	88
7	Discussion	89
7.1	Overall Evaluation	89

7.2 Summary of Contributions	91
7.3 Future Work	92
7.4 Conclusion	94
List of Figures	96
List of Tables	97
Bibliography	99

Abstract

Deep learning models have recently led to significant improvements in a wide variety of tasks. Known as being a very powerful tool capable of generalizing better than traditional machine learning approaches, deep learning models still heavily rely on large quantities of annotated data. As the field of music information retrieval is still subject to data sparsity, automatic music classification remains a challenging problem and numerous models fail at generalizing to out-of-distribution music collections. This project investigates possible directions to follow in order to improve the generalization capacity of deep learning music classifiers. More specifically, we suggest a set of guidelines to be followed in order to address the generalization problem of music classifiers trained on very small datasets. We first propose ways to maximize the amount of information extracted from small datasets through outliers detection and efficient audio data augmentation. We then show that considering the amount of perceptual ambiguity of each classification task through label smoothing can help obtaining more generalizable classification bounds. We also highlight the impact label noise can have in a small dataset setting and explore ways to improve the model's robustness. Finally, we argue that leveraging common knowledge among related classification tasks can result in a more generalizable internal representation learned by the model. To illustrate this assumption, we employ a simple multi-task learning architecture to jointly learn pairs of tasks, and list other interesting axes to be further explored in that direction. All the suggested approaches are experimentally assessed on two state-of-the-art CNN architectures for automatic music classification. They all lead to consistent improvements over baseline models and unveil new relevant questions to rethink the task of automatic music classification.

Keywords: Generalization; Music Classification; Deep Learning.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context and Motivation

The fast growing quantity of music data available, supported by the emergence of numerous streaming platforms has led industrial actors and researchers from the field of music computing to resort to new automatic tools to analyze these large quantities of data. Simultaneously, methods able to handle such amounts of information are directly dependent on new breakthroughs from various fields such as audio signal processing, computer science and mathematics. Over the past decades, the improvements of computational power and memory storage have favored the appearance of data-driven techniques: machine learning algorithms. For the first time, domain experts knowledge is not the only source of information that is leveraged to process and analyze music data. Machine learning algorithms have the capacity to search, extract and make use of valuable information contained in the data in order to automatically carry out the task they are designed for. Although these methods demonstrated a considerable efficiency, they would still strongly rely on human bias induced by musical knowledge. However, for the past 20 years, the rise of more complex learning algorithms has reversed this trend. Based on Rosenblatt's work on perceptrons [1] in 1958, artificial neural networks are now redefining the landscape of how information is processed on a large scale. Further work by Rumelhart, Hinton, and Williams in 1986 [2] on backpropagation algorithms has enabled these

methods to reach a higher level of complexity, resulting in considerable improvements regarding both their capabilities and performances. Nowadays, deep learning has become a very active area of research which is finding applications in almost any field involving large quantities of data.

As a result, the need for effective and reliable automatic tools to analyze music data has fostered the emergence of specifically designed neural network architectures such as in [3]. As of today, these models have shown impressive results in various tasks related to audio, pushing the boundaries of what machines are able to achieve. From problems such as speech recognition [4], source separation [5] or music generation [6], artificial neural networks are also getting a lot of attention to solve tasks related to music analysis. More specifically, a considerable amount of research has been carried out in their application to music classification.

1.2 Challenges

Previous work on statistical learning theory [7] has proposed a general description of the learning problem. In a classification context, let \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} be the data and label spaces respectively. We denote by \mathcal{P} the joint distribution of data and label and each example by $(x, y) \sim \mathcal{P}$. The notion of learning is to accurately find a function $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ which minimizes the expected value of a loss function $\mathcal{L}(f(x), y)$ over the distribution of \mathcal{P} . This expression is referred as the expected risk:

$$R(f | \mathcal{P}) = \int \mathcal{L}(f(x), y) dP(x, y) \quad (1.1)$$

The data distribution \mathcal{P} being unknown in practical situations, a common solution is to approximate the true distribution of the data with a training dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_n, y_n)\}_{n=1}^N$. Then, the expected risk can be estimated by an empirical risk over \mathcal{D} . The problem of expected risk minimization then becomes the empirical risk

minimization problem:

$$\hat{R}(f | \mathcal{P}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathcal{L}(f(x_n), y_n) \quad (1.2)$$

Consequently, controlling the generalization of a learning algorithm consists in constructing an induction principle (i.e finding a function f) that minimizes Equation 1.2. Since the ideal objective is to minimize the expected risk $R(f | \mathcal{P})$, we simulate in practice how well the model would perform on an external dataset while minimizing the empirical risk $\hat{R}(f | \mathcal{P})$. To do so, training data is partitioned into three different sets: a training set, used to train the model; a validation set, used to tune its hyperparameters; a test set, used to measure its generalization performance. On the one hand, the validation set enables to simultaneously choose the optimal hyperparameters values without overfitting the training set or inducing bias at test time. On the other hand, the test set enables to evaluate how well the model would generalize to unseen data. In order to have a qualitative estimation of the generalization ability of a deep learning classifier, it is possible to model the training and validation errors as functions of the number of training examples and the number of parameters [8], as shown in Figure 1. In the former case, it is admitted that having more training data helps improving generalization, Equation 1.2 is minimized as N grows. Indeed, the larger the training set, the fewer regularities induced by the dataset's bias might emerge. Therefore, the model will have to spot strong patterns within the data that are more likely to represent its true distribution. On the contrary, a small training dataset tends to be easier to memorize and makes the model prone to overfitting. Regarding the model's capacity, adding more parameters makes it easier to fit any type of regularity contained in the data, whether it is relevant or not. Therefore, the goal is to design a model that has enough learning capacity to capture useful information from the data, while discarding patterns that are specific to the training set.

The work by Geman, Bienenstock, and Doursat [9] proposes a decomposition of the generalization challenge for deep neural networks. They show that the expectation

Figure 1: Relationship between the number of training examples and training and test error (**left**). Relationship between the number of parameters and training and test error (**right**). Adapted from [8].

of the generalization error is dependent on both the variance and the bias of the learning algorithm. We consider here the case of a squared loss error. We assume that data from both the training and testing set come from the same distribution that we denote by \mathcal{P} . Let \mathbf{x} be a test input sampled from \mathcal{P} and \hat{y} the prediction formulated by the model. We consider that the actual targets y are sampled from $\mathcal{P}(y | \mathbf{x})$. If we treat the predictions \hat{y} as random variables, and suppress the dependence on \mathbf{x} for clarity, the expected squared error decomposes as:

$$\mathbb{E}[(\hat{y} - y)^2] = \underbrace{(\hat{y}_* - \mathbb{E}[\hat{y}]^2)}_{\text{Bias}} + \underbrace{\mathbb{V}(\hat{y})}_{\text{Variance}} + \underbrace{\mathbb{V}(t)}_{\text{Bayes error}} \quad (1.3)$$

where $\hat{y}_* = \mathbb{E}[y | x]$ denotes the best possible predictions that can be made. The first term called *bias* corresponds to the average distance between the model's predictions and the targets. The *variance* refers to the amount of variability in the model's predictions. In other words, this term indicates how much the model overfits the training set. The third term generally called *Bayes error* represents the lowest possible generalization error made if the model fits the data perfectly. Through this decomposition of the generalization error, it is clear that there is a sweet spot that needs to be found between a reasonably small hypotheses space and a complex enough mapping approximated by the model between the inputs and the targets.

This compromise is often referred as the *bias-variance trade-off* in statistics literature and formalizes the qualitative results shown in Figure 1. Even though this decomposition has originally been demonstrated for squared loss functions, the generalization error can be broken down in a similar fashion for classification problems [10]. The problem of improving the generalization ability of a given model goes hand in hand with reducing overfitting. To do so, a wide variety of efficient techniques have been proposed already. Optimization methods [11], [12] or different means of regularization [13], [14] can limit overfitting and push the model to learn more generalizable features during its training process.

Automatically classifying music data has various applications in many domains. Either being a tool for recommendation purposes, musical library organization or large scale music analysis, it appears now as a well studied problem in the field of music information retrieval (MIR). Although it has been thoroughly defined and addressed, it is still far from being considered as solved. Most of the existing work dedicated to music classification has focused on the extraction and the use of relevant features from music, to assign it to different classes based on instruments [15], genre [16, 17], mood [18] or even culture [19]. As described in [20], the performance of each particular classifier can be greatly influenced by different factors. From a general perspective, the data used to train and evaluate these classifiers has a direct impact on the final classification: the quality of the audio, the number of classes or how well the training instances represent the actual data distribution. Deep learning based approaches having the specificity of requiring extensive amounts of data in order to perform well, the majority of these algorithms follow a supervised learning paradigm, where labels corresponding to actual classes are shown during the training phase so that the model learns how to map each input to its corresponding true class. Therefore, large quantities of labelled data are needed, which implies considerable efforts to retrieve and label substantial datasets. Second, once the needed amount of data is gathered, a next step is to ensure it is well curated. Errors during the labelling process can turn out to be very detrimental to the final performance of the classifier [21]. However, assessing the integrity of labels is not always trivial. For example, classes related to notions such as mood or emotions can turn out to be

subjective, and the final annotation heavily depends on the person carrying out the labelling task.

Not complying with these constraints can have dramatic consequences on the learning process of the classifier. A dataset that is not sizeable enough is more likely to fail at representing the actual diversity the model might encounter when dealing with real-world data. As a consequence, a classifier trained on such a dataset might tend to extract information that is solely specific to this very dataset. Similarly, the same issue can arise if this same dataset is corrupted. The mapping between the input and the corresponding classes that the classifier will learn can end up being skewed by erroneous instances. In both of these cases, the final outcome that is to be faced is the incapacity for the model to extract and use relevant information from its training data to perform the classification task it is assigned in real world scenarios.

This thesis aims at providing various approaches to tackle the challenge of generalization in deep learning music classifiers. As previously explained, there exist various strategies that have proven to work well in the context of classification. However in this work, we specifically explore musically motivated approaches. On the one hand, we first focus on the music datasets used for training, and the quality of the information they carry. On the other hand, we propose to look at how the considered classifiers extract knowledge from music data, and whether their learning process can be further improved to better fit the specificities implied by the different classification tasks they are addressing.

1.3 Research Questions

The work carried out in this thesis aims to improve the generalization ability of deep learning music classifiers. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of each method proposed, we use the CNN-based classifiers provided in *Essentia*. *Essentia* is an open-source library that aims at addressing a gap in the audio signal processing and MIR community by implementing a unified pipeline to carry out both audio

features pre-processing and several tasks such as audio classification and tagging [22]. Until now, several classifiers for mood recognition, genre classification or detecting the presence of vocals in music data were based on support vector machines (SVM). However, as described before, many studies now suggest that deep learning and more specifically convolutional neural networks (CNN) can outperform SVM-based algorithms in many tasks. Therefore, a set of CNN-based classifiers has been added to Essentia [23]. These models are trained on small datasets —few hundred instances— that are specific to each classification task. In this context, our initial goal of improving the generalization of these classifiers will be organized along three main approaches. First, we try to improve the quality of the datasets and enhance the potential amount of information that can be extracted from them. Second, we more specifically focus on the label information carried by each dataset. We look for ways to combat negative effects of label noise and address possible ambiguity among different classes. Finally, we explore the notion of knowledge transfer between classification tasks.

We start by investigating the questions related to data efficiency:

- 1) Are there any abnormalities present in the training datasets ? Are the results somehow dependent the nature of each task addressed ?
- 2) How to improve the diversity of the training datasets without any additional data gathering ?

Secondly, in order to improve the efficiency of the learning process, we propose to answer the following questions:

- 1) How can labels ambiguity or subjectivity be translated algorithmically during the training procedure ?
- 2) Given the detrimental effect of label noise on training, can we make the models more robust to mislabelled training instances ?

Finally, we propose to answer the following questions related to knowledge transfer:

- 1) Are there any similarities among the tasks addressed ? If so, how can these be leveraged to improve the performance of these classifiers ?
- 2) Is it possible to effectively predict whether a joint learning strategy will be beneficial for the different tasks addressed?
- 3) What are other possible forms of knowledge transfer among tasks ?

1.4 Contributions

In the first part of this work, we try to answer the data-related questions previously asked using the following approaches:

- 1) We propose a comparative study of two existing outliers detection methods. We describe their sensitivity to particular kinds of outliers and their relationship with the different tasks addressed.
- 2) We experiment with various existing audio data augmentation strategies to enrich our datasets.
- 3) We propose a noise addition method operated directly on mel-spectrograms features aiming at approximating a noise addition in the temporal domain.

In the second part of our work, we bring some modifications to the original models to answer the questions we previously formulated:

- 1) We explore the effect of label smoothing on the training process and its consequences on the overall classification performance. More precisely, we compare 3 existing smoothing strategies relying on different mathematical assumptions and propose a new approach leveraging class information.

- 2) We highlight the importance of the semantic when dealing with automatic music classification.
- 3) Given that loss calculation plays a crucial role throughout training, we show that noise-robust loss functions can be efficient to combat label noise.

In the third part of this report, we finally answer the questions related to knowledge transfer in music classification:

- 1) We propose a multi-task learning architecture to learn different classification tasks simultaneously and promote the sharing of relevant information across them.
- 2) We propose an extension of the multi-task learning approach by making use of pseudo labels—in a semi-supervised fashion—in order to improve the training process and take further advantage of the joint learning setting.
- 3) We give further directions to be explored in which knowledge is transferred among tasks through different angles.

From a more general perspective, we formulate in this work some guidelines to improve the performance of deep learning music classifiers in a context similar to ours. More precisely, we intend to draw research axes going beyond usual regularization methods, where the perceptual and semantic factors are taken into consideration.

Chapter 2

Related Work

2.1 Outliers Detection in Audio Data

2.1.1 Problem Definition

The quality and integrity of the training dataset plays a crucial role in the performance of any learning algorithms. In some cases, training examples can happen to be corrupted, or seem abnormal considering the dataset that is being investigated. These individuals are called outliers. From a general perspective, it is not always obvious to surely assert that a specific instance should be considered as outlier. The first reason is the high specificity of each dataset, which sometimes can push one to think that a particular individual is an outlier, while this same individual actually fits the real world distribution. A second reason is the nature of the data that is manipulated. Recognizing outliers from music data usually requires knowledge from a domain expert, as the notion of outlier itself becomes dependent on both the task that is being considered, and various signal processing and music-related notions. To sum up, detecting outliers in this context has to be performed complying with multiple constraints at the same time. First, it is important to note that an instance can be classified as outlier for a given classification task, while being an inlier for another one. This highlights the high dependency between the task that is considered and the definition of outlier. Second, any dataset comes with an implicit bias due to

its obvious lack of diversity compared to the rest of the data the final model might be exposed to. Therefore, the notion of outlier is implicitly tied to the dataset that is being studied. Consequently, detecting outliers represents only half of the actual process of curating a dataset. The second step is to decide about discarding or not these spotted instances, taking into account the potential loss or gain of information that it implies. Finally, music data can be represented through various forms. One particular outlier detection algorithm can therefore yield different results depending on the data format it operates on.

In general terms, the problem of audio outliers detection can be formulated as follows: we consider a set of N audio instances from which feature vectors have been extracted, $X = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$. Each of these instances has a corresponding label vector $Y = \{\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N\}$ where \mathbf{y}_i belongs to one of the categories considered in the corresponding classification problem. Our goal is to find a set of instance indices that have either a wrong label \mathbf{y}_i , or instances that worsen the performance of the classifier by being too far away from the rest of their respective class. In order to have a general glimpse of how outliers can be detected in audio data, we propose a brief overview of some of the numerous unsupervised algorithms that have previously been used in analogous contexts. We divide these algorithms into two main families: geometrical and statistical.

2.1.2 Geometrical Methods

We refer as geometrical methods, outlier detection algorithms that operate in the features space, involving measures of distance and density among instances. The most simple approach introduced by [24] relies on a similarity value among samples and a dissimilarity threshold above which a certain instance is considered as outlier. Extensions of this method such as the ones introduced in [25] focus on distance measures only within each instance's neighborhood. This way, the resulting algorithms can adapt to various dataset distributions and avoid rejecting non-outlier training examples. Other algorithms referred as *density-based* in [26] use an intermediate step in which they calculate the amount of density around each points. As

an example, the Local Outlier Factor method proposed in [27] calculates a degree of outlierness for each data points based on its local density measure. A point with a lower value of density than its neighbours' indicates that it is isolated in the features space. Therefore, it is assigned a higher degree of outlierness. Other methods such as in [28] first perform a clustering on the whole training dataset. Then assign to each cluster the majority class of the points it contains. Finally, any instance that happens to be in the wrong cluster or too far away from its centroid is considered as outlier.

2.1.3 Statistical Methods

In this category, we grouped outlier detection algorithms that do not only rely on feature values, but also tend to infer about statistical properties of the data. This information is then used to assess the degree of *normality* of each sample. In [29], a variant of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is proposed for detecting outliers. This method has been imagined to be more robust to corrupted observations than the original PCA. It calculates a sparse representation of the data which highlights instances that differ considerably from the rest of the observations. In [30], the authors present a robust categorical regression model that learns a linear mapping between training instances and their corresponding class using a logit function. For each class, the noise term in the linear equation is then used in order to decide whether a particular instance is an outlier of that class. Finally in [31], the authors compute a spectral similarity measure between songs using Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCC) and a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM). They further choose to discard specific instances based on their similarity with their respective neighbors within this similarity space.

2.1.4 Overview

There exist few studies that have quantified the efficiency of outliers detection algorithms on music data. Results obtained in [26], [25] show that each outlier detection approach is sensitive to specific datasets and classification tasks. They also mention

as future research directions to take temporal dependency into account and explore ensemble approaches to take advantage of multiple methods and their own specificities. In [32], Sturm describes the flaws of the very famous *GTZAN* dataset¹. The author highlights various errors that were made while building the dataset and proposes a corrected version. Alternative studies shedding light on corrupted datasets simultaneously preserve the integrity of further research in the broad field of MIR, and propose an experimentation ground for data cleansing algorithms such as outliers detection methods.

2.2 Audio Data Augmentation

2.2.1 Problem Definition

The performance of deep learning models heavily depends on the amount of data available for training. In our scenario, most of the datasets considered are composed of a few hundred instances. Therefore, there is a high risk of explicitly learning regular elements strictly contained in these datasets (such as timbral, rhythmic or artist information as explained in [33]). Building a dataset is a tedious process that involves lots of resources and efforts to guarantee the quality of the data gathered, and the integrity of the labels provided. To avoid this exhausting step, numerous works have resorted to data augmentation techniques. Data augmentation aims to generate new training instances by applying transformations to existing samples from the actual dataset, in a way that labels can still be retrieved [34]. Originally, the most common field employing this strategy is computer vision, where various transformations can be applied to images before the training phase: cropping, rotating or adding noise. However, applying such transformations to image-like representations of audio data can sometimes lead to issues such as mislabelling of certain instances, or can simply lack of musical sense and would not bring any significant improvement.

In order to preserve labels' integrity, it is important to consider various musically-motivated constraints when augmenting an audio dataset and the different data

¹<http://marsyas.info/download/datasets>

formats it can be applied to. Here, we propose an overview of audio data augmentation strategies that have successfully been applied in the field of MIR. From this, our next step will consist in empirically determining which are the most appropriate ones for each classification task we consider, and their potential influence on the classification results. To this end, the said transformations will exclusively be applied to each training set, leaving the test sets untouched in order to guarantee a fair and unbiased comparison of the resulting classification outcomes. Moreover, as described in [35], it is to be noted that in order to prevent the model from explicitly learning the audio transformations, it is common to chain them in series to form a more complex final transformation.

2.2.2 Existing Methods

Data augmentation can either be applied to raw audio, or on the set of features that is extracted from it. In the latter case, transformations can be efficiently applied within the data-processing pipeline such as after calculating spectrograms as in [36]. This setting also requires less computational power and memory than operating on audio waveforms. In broader terms, data augmentation techniques can perform modifications on the temporal and pitch-related information such as pitch-shifting, pitch-scaling or time-scaling [35]. They can also consist in applying various audio effects such as reverb, saturation or distortion [37]. The convolution operation is also commonly used, when for example one wants to imitate the rendering obtained with a mobile microphone or the recording effect of a room such as in [38]. Finally, various mixing effects can also be employed as data augmentation strategies such as in [35] and [36]. For example, these effects can be compression, equalization, panning or modifying the gain. The choice of the subset of data these transformations are applied to is essential. When only performed on the training set, keeping the testing set untouched, we can improve the robustness of a classifier and make it less dependent on subtle patterns it contains. However, when applied at both training and testing time, audio data augmentation serves as a way to evaluate the robustness of the classifier as we directly measure how tolerant its decision boundary is with regard to the transformations introduced. It is important here to take into account

that most studies and reviews carried out in the field of audio data augmentation usually evaluate their transformations on a particular task such as music genre classification [35], [36] or instrument classification such as [37] and [39]. Even though they propose a thorough comparative study of each data augmentation strategy’s influence on their model’s performance, it seems that there is a high dependency between the efficiency of each strategy and the task they aim at improving. As we deal here with multiple MIR tasks, we will therefore base ourselves on the most common approaches and experimentally determine what are the most suitable data augmentation strategies for the different tasks being addressed.

2.3 Label Smoothing

2.3.1 Formulation

It is common for datasets to come with a certain amount of noise. In case of a classification problem, this noise can correspond to mislabelled instances. In this context, maximizing $\log p(x | y)$ when y is a mistake can greatly penalize the model and decrease the efficiency of the learning process, as neural networks are able to fit any arbitrary labels [12]. To address this issue, it is possible to refer to the previous outliers detection strategies described earlier in this report. However, it can be useful to simultaneously model label noise in an explicit manner [40]. If we consider a model with k softmax output values, a *uniform label smoothing* models the potential presence of noise by transforming the hard 0 or 1 labels into soft targets of $\frac{1-\epsilon}{k-1}$ and ϵ respectively. Intuitively, *label smoothing* tends to discourage the model from pursuing hard probabilities without penalizing its correct classifications [41]. Even though the term ϵ becomes an additional hyper-parameter that needs to be optimized, *label smoothing* has proven to be efficient in various deep learning applications, especially in the field of computer vision [42]. In the presence of label noise, label smoothing has also appeared as a competitive method compared to loss-correction approaches [43]. Finally, by reducing the gap between hard labels and the predictions, label smoothing has the power to improve the generalization capacity of various deep learning models [44], [45].

2.3.2 Audio-Related Applications

Smoothing labels is a strategy that has already been employed in some audio-related applications. In the field of sound events recognition, label smoothing has enabled to improve the performance of classifiers by simultaneously acting as a mean of regularization and reducing the influence of possibly wrongly annotated training instances [46], [47]. In the field of speech processing, label smoothing has also enabled speech recognition systems to reach higher level of accuracies by penalizing their low entropy outputs. As an example in [48], a regularization term is added to their Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) model's loss function in order to reduce the influence of blank symbols predominantly predicted by their model. In [49], the authors propose a speech emotion recognition model that makes use of label smoothing in order to alleviate the problem of imbalanced emotional classes in their training set. Finally, label smoothing can also yield improvements in music-related applications. In [50], the authors show the effectiveness of learning label distributions instead of hard labels in a regression setting. The loss function proposed in their work, referred as Histogram Loss, consists in converting original targets into a target distributions. Their approach brings slight improvements over baseline linear models on predicting the release year of songs from audio features using the Song Year dataset [51]. Finally in [52], a Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) based probabilistic model is used to smooth music tagging data in order to address the issue of data sparsity. In the case of small training datasets, they show that augmenting the data with this analogous smoothing strategy improves the performance of their music tagging model.

2.3.3 Motivations

Label smoothing has the potential to simultaneously preserve the information contained in the data, while limiting the negative effects of corrupted labels. In some cases, the classification task can be very difficult to learn, as the classes rely on perceptual features that can hardly be modelled through the data preprocessing stage. For example, music mood classification can imply a high ambiguity among

labels [53]. In such contexts, the noise previously mentioned not only accounts for mislabelled instances, but for training samples that tend to be very close to the perceptual classification bound. If we consider the case of determining whether a song is happy or not, then it is highly probable that some of the songs contained in the training set will be located at the perceptual limit between the two classes. Therefore, label smoothing appears to be a way to address this issue by artificially modelling the uncertainty of the labelling process. Throughout its learning phase, the model will not be optimized to reach high probabilities for such instances, which intuitively prevents important penalizing errors in case of unreliable labels.

2.4 Loss Functions

2.4.1 Problem Definition

Neural networks generally aim at mapping a set of inputs to a set of outputs from their training data. Their high efficiency is partly due to their important number of parameters that are optimized throughout the learning process. The huge amount of possible combinations requires to rethink the problem of parameters search as an optimization problem. This way, it is possible to explore the space of parameters values in order to come up with the best performing model. The evaluation of the model for each set of parameters values is made possible through the use of loss functions. In the context of neural networks, loss functions typically represent the amount of error committed by the model on the training dataset. The exploration of the parameters space is therefore done such as to minimize the value of the loss function [54]. We previously described the potentially detrimental effect of noisy data on the learning process of deep learning models and how it can hamper their performance. Here, it is clear that having corrupted labels explicitly skews the model's evaluation for a given set of parameters. Consequently, the overall optimization process may not lead to the actual best possible model. Another way to approach this issue is to look for loss functions that are inherently robust to noise present in the data.

2.4.2 Existing Approaches

Learning in the presence of label noise is a problem that has been thoroughly addressed [55]. Numerous works have attempted to propose noise robust loss functions in the context of deep neural networks. A first theoretical result guaranteeing the robustness to noise of a loss function has been proposed in [56] for binary classification, and in [57] for multi-class classification. A noise function is said to be tolerant to noise in classification problem with c classes if the noise rate $\tau < \frac{c-1}{c}$ and:

$$\sum_{j=1}^c \mathcal{L}(f(x; \Theta), y = j) = C, \forall x \in \mathcal{X}, \forall f, \quad (2.1)$$

where f is the label mapping function learned by the model using the loss function \mathcal{L} and C is a constant. Under this condition, the model trained on noisy data has the same misclassification probability as a model trained on a dataset free of noise. When working on a classification task, the categorical cross-entropy (CCE) is the most commonly used loss function, which usually leads to fast convergence and good generalization. However in [57], it is shown that the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is more robust to noise as it treats all data points equally and complies with the aforementioned assumption. Based on this result, the Generalized Cross Entropy (GCE) is proposed in [58], which combines both the positive effects of CCE and MAE. Additionally, [59] propose the Symmetric Cross Entropy (SCE). Inspired by the symmetry of the Kullback-Leibler divergence, they show that adding symmetry to the CCE loss by combining it with a noise tolerance term improves the robustness of the model while learning. Among many more approaches, some loss functions can also operate as *label refurbishment*. As described in [60], a *refurbished* label can be calculated as a convex combination of the noisy label and the current prediction of the network. A first method employing this strategy was the *Bootstrapping* loss function introduced in [61]. The intuition behind this approach is that in the case of a noisy training example, the corresponding loss would be smoothed out by the model's confidence on that specific example. In other words, if the label is wrong, the model's prediction on that corresponding training example might be headed towards

the opposite direction (the other class in a binary classification task). The resulting loss value will therefore be smaller than with a classical CCE. Beyond the use of robust loss functions or label refurbishment, there exists a variety of deep learning methods for overcoming label noise [60] such as loss correction, loss reweighting or specific noise-adaptation layers.

In the field of MIR, it is common to go beyond classical loss functions based on the nature of the problem addressed. For example in [62], the authors use a Partial Categorical Cross-Entropy as their dataset misses some ground truth labels. In [63], a comparative study of different loss functions is carried out for a polyphonic music sequence transduction and for music source separation in [64]. However, in the context of music classification, Cross-Entropy based loss functions remain the most common ones. As previously described, CCE can be sensitive to label noise and negatively impact the learning process by putting too much emphasis on corrupted labels. In the context of acoustic events recognition with noisy labels, [46] proposes to use the GCE loss. It is also argued that neural networks tend to learn hard examples towards the end of their training phase. Therefore, a two-stage training process is introduced during which the network is trained on the whole dataset for a fixed number of epochs using a noise-robust loss function. Then, high-loss instances are discarded from gradient updates to preserve the model from problematic training examples.

2.5 Multi-Task Learning

2.5.1 Problem Definition

Multi-Task learning (MTL) [65] is a paradigm that aims at improving the generalization of machine learning models by leveraging information contained in the training signal of related tasks. When applied to deep learning, it consists of having one single network simultaneously learning multiple tasks instead of having task-specific models solving them independently. This type of learning setting has been motivated by different factors [66]. First, MTL appears as a way to address the

issue of data sparsity in certain domains by using knowledge extracted from other auxiliary tasks and their respective datasets. Second, MTL models have recently proven to achieve better performance than their counterparts, task-specific models, especially in the fields of Natural Language Processing or Computer Vision. Third, as MTL models are exposed to different sources of data during training, they tend to formulate richer and more general hypotheses with regard to the underlying data distribution, which ultimately reduces overfitting and can greatly improve generalization to unseen data. Finally, training one single model to simultaneously perform different tasks can greatly reduce the overall computational cost compared to task-specific models. Even when an auxiliary task is used to improve a main one, MTL models tend to converge faster and therefore, have a lower need in computational resources than traditional approaches [65]. As a formal definition of MTL, we refer the one proposed in [66]:

Multi-Task Learning: *Given m learning tasks $\{\tau_i\}_{i=1}^m$ where all tasks or a subset of them are related, multi-task learning aims to learn these m tasks together to improve the learning of a model for each task τ_i by using the knowledge contained in all or some of these tasks.*

As of today, MTL has been a subject of great interest in the machine learning community [65], [66], [67]. By merging training examples of various tasks together, MTL applies an implicit constraints over the parameters of the model that are shared across tasks. As the optimization process not only complies with a single task anymore, the shared part of the network is therefore driven towards good representations for all tasks simultaneously [41]. However, it is sometimes possible for the final performance to be degraded when tasks do not share a significant statistical relationship [41], which is commonly referred as *negative transfer* [68].

2.5.2 Application to Audio Data

Besides the existing taxonomies of MIR tasks that have been proposed in [20] for example, no thorough studies of their mutual relationships have been carried out. However, the numerous advantages brought by MTL approaches have led the MIR

community to leverage possible connections among music related problems. First, the area of automatic music transcription has seen great improvements using MTL models. Tempo, beat [69] or fundamental frequency estimation [70] and melody extraction [71] are problems involving different sub-tasks, which when learned together, can achieve higher performance than task-specific approaches. Similarly, the vast area of source separation has taken advantage of related tasks to improve the efficiency of audio source [72] or singing voice separation models [73]. Finally, audio classification and recognition tasks have also benefited from the MTL paradigm. In [74], sound event recognition and localization are addressed jointly by a single model that surpasses baseline models in both tasks. In [75], the authors propose a MTL model for a weakly supervised sound event detection problem, where data denoising and recognition are learned jointly. Finally in [76], a self-supervised MTL method is introduced to pre-train music encoders, which improves the effectiveness of a simple Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) further used to solve various music classification tasks.

2.5.3 Disjoint Datasets

Going back to the formal definition proposed in [66], MTL approaches can be characterized as follows: in a supervised learning setting, a task τ_i is provided with a dataset \mathcal{D}_i that is composed of n_i training examples: $\mathcal{D}_i = \{\mathbf{x}_j^i, y_j^i\}_{j=1}^{n_i}$ where $\mathbf{x}_j^i \in \mathbb{R}^{d_i}$ is the j th training example in τ_i and y_j^i is its label. The case where different tasks are in the same feature space, which implies $\mathcal{D}_i = \mathcal{D}_j, \forall i \neq j$ is called homogeneous feature MTL. On the contrary, different feature spaces among tasks is referred as heterogeneous feature MTL. Similarly, the same differentiation can be made regarding the nature of the tasks addressed: regression or classification; and the learning paradigm followed: supervised, semi-supervised, unsupervised or reinforcement learning. The most common setting in MTL is the homogeneous feature one, where output tasks can be of any nature. In this situation, one dataset is usually associated with various outputs, corresponding to each task addressed. However, it is very common for datasets to be provided with only one type of label. This setting is usually referred as MTL with disjoint datasets [77]. Conforming with

more traditional MTL settings would require the construction of a unified dataset, which would imply an exhaustive labelling process. In order to overcome this issue, several methods have been proposed. In [77], the authors propose an alternating directional optimization method to efficiently learn from heterogeneous human action classification and human behavior captioning datasets. This method is extended in [78], where the network also augments each task with the unlabelled data from the other one in a semi-supervised learning fashion. Finally, in [79], a Label Embedding Layer is added to the model in order to model the relationship among tasks. They also train a Label Transfer Network (LTN) which produces soft labels for the unlabelled task at a given training iteration.

From a more intuitive point of view, it seems sensible to imagine the overall processing of music data as encompassing its inherent nature, where most of the tasks addressed, either low or high level, tend to relate to each other. MTL approaches aim to move towards the modelling of music as whole, where information about some of its aspects can unveil new knowledge about its general organization.

Chapter 3

Experimental Setting

The deep learning models proposed in the Essentia library [22] aim at solving different common music classification tasks. In this chapter, we give a brief overview of these models: their architecture, the training datasets and the external audio collections used for testing. We also introduce the training and evaluation methodologies that are followed throughout the different experiments carried out in this work.

3.1 Tasks Addressed & Datasets

The current deep learning models provided within the Essentia library are trained on in-house music collections from the Music Technology Group (MTG) [23], which are summarized in Table 1. These datasets have also been used in different projects such as AcousticBrainz [80]. The authors in [23] claim that these datasets, despite their relatively small size, represent a classical use-case of audio analysis in limited data scenarios. Moreover, it is important to note that some of these collections might contain problematic instances, such as audio files that have been mislabelled. Unless mentioned otherwise, the models studied in this work are trained on mel-spectrograms with 96 bands. Section 4.2 uses mel-spectrogram representations as it operates directly on the input data of the networks. Finally, as we hope to give general guidelines, the rest of the experiments carried out in Sections 4.1 and 5.1 use MFCC representations as each of their coefficients tend to be decorrelated among

each other compared to mel-spectrogram features. The main motivation is that MFCC will tend to carry less redundant information and, in case of linear transformations, will yield more meaningful results. Additionally, MFCC representations are widely used in a variety of audio-related problems and therefore, each of the methods proposed can be directly adapted to any particular use-case.

Datasets	Classes	Size
genre-dortmund	alternative, blues, electronic, folk-country, funksoulrnb, jazz, pop, raphiphop, rock	1820 exc.
genre-gtzan	blues, classic, country, disco, hip hop, jazz, metal, pop, reggae, rock	1000 exc.
genre-rosamerica	classic, dance, hip hop, jazz, pop, rhythm and blues, rock, speech	400 ft.
mood-acoustic	acoustic, not acoustic	321 ft.
mood-electronic	electronic, not electronic	332 ft./exc.
mood-aggressive	aggressive, not aggressive	280 ft.
mood-relaxed	relaxed, not relaxed	446 ft./exc.
mood-happy	happy, not happy	302 exc.
mood-sad	sad, not sad	230 ft./exc.
mood-party	party, not party	349 exc.
danceability	danceable, not danceable	306 ft.
voice/instrumental	voice, instrumental	1000 exc.
gender	female, male	3311 ft.
timbre	bright, dark	3000 exc.
tonal/atonal	atonal, tonal	345 exc.

Table 1: MTG In-house music collections (ft.: full tracks, exc.: excerpts). Adapted from [23].

3.2 Deep Learning Models

3.2.1 Architectures

In this work, we evaluate the relevance of the methods we proposed on the different architectures chosen in [23] and [81]. These two types of deep learning models mainly differ from each other in their overall number of parameters, and the shape of their convolutional filters. Therefore, the way they extract information throughout their

learning process will tend to be different, which as we will see, has an influence on their results on each specific classification task addressed.

- MusiCNN: a convolutional neural network that aims at capturing timbral and temporal patterns using vertical and horizontal convolution operations [82], [83]. The model is composed 6 layers and has a total of 787,000 trainable parameters.
- VGG: originally designed for computer vision tasks, this convolutional neural network is built as a stack of 33 convolutional filters. Two different versions of this model are considered: VGG-I, which has 5 layers of 128 convolutional filters each and a total of 605,000 trainable parameters; VGG-II which uses the configuration from [84], with a number of output units set to 3087 and 62 million trainable parameters in total.

3.2.2 Training Strategies

Two training strategies are originally followed in [81]. The first one consists of a traditional approach where the parameters of each model are randomly initialized, and the training process is carried out from scratch. However, due to the small number of training instances in each dataset, the authors also suggest a transfer learning-based strategy. Each model is first pre-trained on one of the following audio tagging datasets:

- MSD-train: A collection of 200,000 tracks from the Million Song Dataset [51], each track was annotated using the 50 Lastfm tags most frequent in the dataset¹.
- AudioSet: A collection of 1.8 million YouTube audio clips with the AudioSet taxonomy [85].

¹<http://millionsongdataset.com/lastfm>

It is then fine tuned on the in-house training datasets for a smaller number of epochs than the traditional approach, as the model tends to converge faster. Each model is trained on mini-batches of 32 samples, where each training sample corresponds to a 3 second long extract from each audio file chosen randomly. The optimizer used is Adam, and the models trained from scratch are trained for a total of 600 epochs, while the transfer learning ones during only 150 epochs. The default learning rate is set to 0.001, and reduces by half after 75 epochs if the validation loss has not decreased. Unless mentioned otherwise, all the experimentations carried out in this report will use a categorical cross-entropy loss as originally in [23].

3.2.3 Evaluation Process

Once each model has been trained following the aforementioned strategies, it is then evaluated on external data. The work carried out in [86] highlights the importance of varying the data source on which a given classifier is evaluated. In their study, the authors show that despite performing well on their training datasets in a cross-validation setting, numerous classifiers tend to generalize poorly when being evaluated on external audio cross-collections. Therefore, given the small size of the training sets used, the authors in [81] argue that the 5-fold cross-validation performance is unreliable, and propose to use the following some of these external audio collections:

- MSD-test, which is the test set of the MSD dataset with Lastfm tags [86].
- The split-0 test set from the MTG-Jamendo dataset² for music tagging, composed of 11,000 tracks [87].

The overall data splitting strategy is the following: for training, each split from the 5-fold cross-validation is then further divided into 80% for training, and 20% for validation. Finally, the evaluation is then done by re-training each model on 80% of the whole training dataset, while keeping 20% for validation and the aforementioned cross-collections are used as test sets.

²<http://mtg.github.io/mtg-jamendo-dataset>

3.3 Methodology

3.3.1 Training Procedure

Throughout our experiments, we choose to follow the same training procedures as the ones we previously described. More specifically, the 5-fold cross-validation setting can enable us to measure the influence of our experiments on the way information is extracted from the training datasets. Moreover, as we use the original performance results as baselines, it is necessary to comply with the same training strategy to allow for a fair comparison against the improvements we hope to bring throughout this work. Therefore, proposed method will be evaluated for both the MusiCNN and VGG models, each pre-trained on the MSD-train audio collection, by comparing the 5-fold cross-validation performance on the training datasets.

3.3.2 Evaluation Procedure

The research carried out in this work essentially aims at improving the generalization of the previously mentioned deep learning classifiers on external data. Therefore, the evaluation procedure is the most crucial step in assessing what are the approaches that led to a generalization improvement. In the same way as for training, we cautiously ensure that the comparison with baseline models generalization performance is fair. To this end, the evaluation of our experiments is done on the same external audio collection as for the baseline models: the MTG-Jamendo dataset. More precisely, each experiment will make use of both models architectures in their transfer-learning version, and their weighted classification accuracy on the external audio collection against the corresponding baseline models will be assessed. In the tables presenting the results, we will highlight in **bold** both significant changes (independent samples t-test with $p > 0.05$) in the 5-fold cross-validation results and generalization improvements made on the MTG-Jamendo dataset.

Chapter 4

Data Processing

The first axes of research we propose to look at deals with the both the quality and the quantity of training instances available for each classification task. As previously described, it is important to ensure about labels coherence. To do so, we look at two different outliers detection methods and carry out an evaluation based on a subjective labelling process on a subset of datasets. Despite the success of data augmentation for deep learning models, augmenting audio data is still a challenging problem. We therefore list label-preserving audio transformations and design an augmentation policy in order to increase the amount of training data for each task.

4.1 Audio Outliers Detection

We conduct several experiments using two outliers detection algorithms that have previously been employed for audio data. Both methods operate directly in the feature space but rely on different mathematical assumptions. We introduce each algorithm and detail our evaluation procedure. We finally analyze the results and conclude about the general task of audio outliers detection.

4.1.1 MP-Reject

The notion of Mutual Proximity (MP) [25] reformulates the measure of distance in the feature space so that two objects that are sharing similar neighbors are closer

to each other, while two objects with dissimilar neighborhoods are pushed apart. The main motivation of this approach is to counter the effect of densely distributed groups of instances in the data. To compute MP, we assume that the distances $D_{x,i=1,\dots,N}$ from an object x to all other objects in the dataset follow a probability distribution $P(X)$. This way, any distance $D_{x,y}$ can be reinterpreted as the probability of y being the nearest neighbor of x , given their distance $D_{x,y}$ and the probability distribution $P(X)$:

$$P(X > D_{x,y}) = 1 - P(X < D_{x,y}) = 1 - \mathcal{F}_x(D_{x,y}) \quad (4.1)$$

where \mathcal{F} is the cumulative distribution function. MP is therefore defined as the probability that y is the nearest neighbor of x given $P(X)$ and x is the nearest neighbor of y given $P(Y)$:

$$MP(D_{x,y}) = P(X > D_{x,y} \cap Y > D_{y,x}) \quad (4.2)$$

As in the original paper, we assume here that the distance distributions follow a Gaussian distribution. Moreover in our implementation, we make the assumption that $P(X)$ and $P(Y)$ are independent, so we do not have to estimate the joint probability distributions $P(X, Y)$ for all distance pairs $d_{x,y}$. In [88], the authors experimentally observe that this assumption does not affect the final results and greatly reduces the computational cost. The final outlier score of x is then given by:

$$S^{MP}(x) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (1 - MP(x, NN_i(x))) \quad (4.3)$$

where $NN_i(x)$ denotes the i th nearest neighbour of x in the feature space and k , which represents the number of neighbours considered, is a hyperparameter that is arbitrarily set beforehand. The final outlier score $S^{MP}(x)$ that is obtained lies

between 0 and 1, therefore, x is eventually considered as outlier if:

$$S^{MP}(x) > \alpha \quad (4.4)$$

where α is a decision threshold that is experimentally set.

4.1.2 Local Outlier Factor

The Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [27] is an analogous yet different approach which specifically focuses on the notion of density within the data. In the case of a dataset that is densely distributed, some points may have shorter average distance to their neighbors, and vice versa. Let the notion of k -reachability distance be expressed as:

$$\text{k-reachDist}(P, O) = \max(k - \text{distance}(P), d(O, P)) \quad (4.5)$$

where k -distance(P) corresponds to the distance value between P and its nearest neighbor k . The k -reachDist(P, O) represents the distance from O to P , with a lower bound being the distance from P to its nearest neighbor. Then, the local reachability density of a point is given by the inverse of the average local reachability distance of its k -nearest neighbors:

$$\text{lrd}(P) = 1 / \left(\frac{\sum_{P_0 \in \text{neighbors}_k} k - \text{reachDist}(P, P_0)}{|\text{neighbors}_k(P)|} \right) \quad (4.6)$$

Then, the LOF measure is calculated by taking the ratio of the local reachability densities of the k -nearest neighbors against the point P :

$$\text{LOF}(P) = \frac{\sum_{P_0 \in \text{neighbors}_k(P)} \text{lrd}(P_0)}{\text{lrd}(P) |\text{neighbors}_k(P)|} \quad (4.7)$$

Since LOF uses the ratio instead of the distance as the outlier score, it is able to detect outliers in clusters with varying densities.

4.1.3 Multi-Class Version

Even though the MP-Reject and LOF methods are designed to model more accurately the inner organization of the data, they tend to be sensitive to different factors that negatively impact their performance. Since no audio quality evaluation has been carried out beforehand for each dataset, there happen to be audio files that acoustically differ from the rest of the data. These disparities can either be explained by poor quality recordings or variations in loudness or gain levels. As a consequence, since LOF and MP-Reject are applied to each class individually, they have a tendency to consider these "problematic" files as outliers of their respective class. However in most cases, despite their purely quality-based differences, these data points do belong to the classes they are assigned to. Therefore, we propose to address this issue by introducing additional knowledge about the outlieriness of each data point. To do so, we not only calculate the outlier score $S_{in}(x)$ of each data point from its assigned class, but also its outlier score from the other class(es) $S_{out}(x)$. Finally, a decision function that takes as input both $S_{in}(x)$ and $S_{out}(x)$ returns whether the data point x should be considered as outlier. Intuitively, this methods consists in comparing the degree of abnormality of each data point within each class. If an audio file suffers from a bad quality, or other mastering effects that make it "sound different" from the other data points, then this should be the case for any class within the dataset. Therefore, we would obtain $S_{in}(x) \simeq S_{out}(x)$. On the contrary, if there are some disparities in the abnormality scores across classes for a given point x , then we consider two cases:

- If $S_{in}(x) < S_{out}(x)$: the data point x is considered as an inlier.
- If $S_{in}(x) > \alpha \times S_{out}(x)$: the data point x is considered as an outlier, given a certain threshold α .

The threshold value α is set empirically. A higher value of α pushes the method to be more specific to very singular data points, while lower α values make the outliers detection method for sensitive to any data points. Besides the apparent simplicity

of this decision function, it manages to model a more accurate notion of outlier, which adapts itself to the configuration of the data and the classification task that is being considered.

4.1.4 Subjective Evaluation

One main challenge that is faced in the outliers detection process is the evaluation criteria. As no a priori knowledge is given on the potential presence of outliers within the considered datasets, there is no actual ground-truth to compare the detected data points with. However, the small size of the datasets allows us to formulate a subjective evaluation process in order to compare the detected outliers, with perceptually spotted ones. This brief evaluation process has two main goals:

1. Choose optimized threshold values.
2. Compare the outliers detection algorithms: LOF, MP-Reject and their respective multi-class version.

Data Representations

The outliers detection process is applied to each dataset after extracting MFCC features. This representation enables us to conserve both temporal and frequency-related information, while containing various indications about the timbre content, the tempo or the energy. We then average each MFCC along the temporal axis and finally obtain a vector representation x_i of each audio extract such that $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^{13}$, where the dimension of x_i corresponds to the arbitrary number of MFCC coefficients used.

Strategy

We define an evaluation strategy in order to assess the efficiency of each outliers detection method and tune each algorithm's hyperparameters. We first start by picking three different classification tasks from the ones listed in Table 1: we make

use of the work carried out in [32] on the *GTZAN* dataset, which highlights problematic instances from this dataset and will serve as a ground truth. Additionally, we select two binary classification tasks which can be characterized by different levels of ambiguity: happy/non-happy and relaxed/non-relaxed. We then subjectively listen to each song and manually annotate the ones that should be recognized as outliers with respect to their class. In this context, due to the small size of the training datasets, we consider that discarding actual outliers is as equally important as keeping relevant training instances. Therefore, we assess the performance of each method by calculating values of precision, recall and F1 regarding the outliers detected:

- Precision: Will serve as an indication about the relevance of the training samples detected by each algorithm. The higher the precision, the bigger the proportion of true outliers within all the data points detected by the algorithm.
- Recall: Highlights how efficient each algorithm has been at spotting outliers. The bigger the recall measure, the bigger the percentage of true outliers recognized among the total of outliers.
- F1: Measures an average between the precision and the recall, which in our case, will give a general appreciation of the performance of each algorithm.

Finally, we also report the number of outliers detected by each algorithm in order to guide our selection towards the most precise method, despite maybe a smaller F1 measure.

Results

In order to compare these different methods, we started by performing a grid search to find the optimal values of thresholds to use in each algorithm: for the MP-Reject algorithm, we use a step size of 0.1 within the range $[0; 1]$; for the multi-class version, denoted as MP-Reject Double, we use a step size of 0.1 within the range $[1; 2]$. It is important to note that for the LOF algorithm, the threshold is

fixed to -1.5 in the implementation proposed by [89]. Additionally, we restrain our general parameters search by using an arbitrary number of $k = 5$ neighbours for each algorithm. The optimal threshold values were selected while only considering the F-measure calculated with regard to the outliers detected, results reported are the ones obtained with these optimal values. Finally, when all the outliers detected are irrelevant, we arbitrarily report the results obtained with the lowest value of threshold.

Class	Method	α	Outliers	Precision	Recall	F1
Happy	MP-R	0.3	7	0.43	0.23	0.30
Happy	MP-Rdb	1.7	5	0.60	0.23	0.33
Not Happy	MP-R	0.3	5	0.20	0.25	0.22
Not Happy	MP-Rdb	1.0	20	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 2: Experimental results of MP-Reject for the happy/not happy dataset.

From the first series of experiments carried out on the happy/not happy dataset, results reported in Table 2 highlight the strong dependency between the task addressed, each of its classes and the performance of each algorithm. For the "happy" class, almost all method combinations recognize the same amount of outliers, however the multi-class method (MP-Rdb) seems to provide a more refined selection of outliers, which can be deduced from the precision values. However, the diversity of the "not happy" class leads the multi-class method to recognize wrong instances as outliers, where the single one seems to better capture it and manages to spot 1 outlier out of 4.

Class	Method	α	Outliers	Precision	Recall	F1
Relaxed	MP-R	0.2	59	0.03	0.40	0.06
Relaxed	MP-Rdb	1.0	12	0.00	0.00	0.00
Not Relaxed	MP-R	0.4	7	1.00	0.44	0.61
Not Relaxed	MP-Rdb	1.6	18	0.50	0.56	0.53

Table 3: Experimental results of MP-Reject for the relaxed/not relaxed dataset.

Throughout the subjective recognition of outliers from the "relaxed" class, most of the selected audio extracts were differing from the others only regarding the presence of rhythmical elements. Therefore, we can see in Table 3 that this strong ambiguity

has led the MP-Reject method to spot very few of them, regardless of the audio format used or the version of the algorithm. On the other hand, the "not relaxed" class being more straightforward, there is a considerable gain in performance. Even though the basic MP-Reject algorithm yields the best F1 measure, it is worth noting that the MP-Rdb spots more actual outliers, while not discarding too many inliers.

Class	Method	α	Outliers	Precision	Recall	F1
Happy	LOF	-1.5	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
Happy	LOFdb	1.2	63	0.14	0.69	0.24
Not Happy	LOF	-1.5	4	0.25	0.25	0.25
Not Happy	LOFdb	1.0	18	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 4: Experimental results of LOF for the happy/not happy dataset.

Results reported in Table 4 show that almost 70% of outliers from the "happy" class are well recognized by the multi-class LOF algorithm, despite a relatively low precision value. Concerning the "not happy" task, the same conclusion can be drawn than with the MP-Reject algorithm. The multi-class version of the LOF algorithm does not manage to encompass the diversity of the "not happy" class. Although the same amount of relevant outliers is detected, the original version of the algorithm seems to be more efficient in this setting.

Class	Method	α	Outliers	Precision	Recall	F1
Relaxed	LOF	-1.5	2	0.00	0.00	0.00
Relaxed	LOFdb	1.2	1	1.00	0.20	0.33
Not Relaxed	LOF	-1.5	4	1.00	0.25	0.40
Not Relaxed	LOFdb	1.1	17	0.53	0.56	0.55

Table 5: Experimental results of LOF for the relaxed/not relaxed dataset.

When the LOF algorithm is applied to the relaxed/not relaxed dataset, the multi-class version seems to considerably outperform its original version. As reported in Table 5, the multi-class LOF efficiently spots one true outlier from the "happy" class. For the "not happy" class, it recognizes more than half of the true outliers, and 56% of the spotted training instances are actual outliers we subjectively listed.

As described in [32], the *GTZAN* dataset includes some problematic instances, which can negatively affect a final model when used within the training dataset.

Method	α	Outliers	Precision	Recall	F1
MP-R	0.25	141	0.04	0.10	0.05
MP-Rdb	1.4	90	0.04	0.08	0.06

Table 6: Experimental results of MP-Reject for the GTZAN dataset.

The author lists different types of corrupted audio samples: repetitions, mislabelled and distorted. Here, we only selected the mislabelled data points, which represent a total of 47 extracts out of the 1000 that compose the dataset. The "multi-class" version of each outliers detection algorithm has been slightly adapted so that it can operate on datasets containing more than 2 classes. The main principle remains the same: for each training instance x_i in the dataset, the outlier score $S_{in}(x)$ calculated from its assigned class is compared against $S_{out}^j(x_i)$ where $j \in \{1; \dots; K\}$ and K denotes the total number of classes of the dataset. Results reported in Table 6 show that the MP-Reject method performs very poorly on this dataset, regardless of the algorithm's version employed. However, the LOF algorithm seems to better fit the organization of the data among the different classes. Although almost 20% of actual outliers spotted by the multi-class version operating on the MFCC features, these results are achieved by discarding more than 10% of the overall dataset, which could potentially be more detrimental than keeping the outliers.

Method	α	Outliers	Precision	Recall	F1
LOF	-1.5	29	0.03	0.02	0.03
LOFdb	1.1	158	0.06	0.19	0.09

Table 7: Experimental results of LOF for the GTZAN dataset.

From a global perspective, the detection of outliers in the field of genre classification faces various challenges that are directly related to the perceptual notion of genre. First, the cohesion of each genre can greatly differ: classical music has a way more specific timbre signature than pop music, which tends to encompass an important variety of musical formations and instruments. Second, the frontier between each genre considerably fluctuates. Some genres happen to be very akin to each other, which increases the probability of having songs located at the frontier separating them. However, as the notion of genre is also dependent on the artist or the band,

a song from a Blues artist that perceptually sounds closer to Rock will usually still be considered as Blues in the music genre taxonomy.

4.1.5 Conclusion

The different experiments carried out here highlight the high dependency existing between how well a given algorithm will perform, and the class it is operating on. There does not seem to be any trend emerging, however, we do highlight that the improvement we proposed for both algorithms improve results in some particular cases. The multi-class version of each algorithm usually manages to capture a more accurate subset of training instances. In the context of limited quantities of labelled data, it is important for the outliers detection process to preserve the integrity and diversity of the overall dataset. By comparing relative outlieriness scores from each class, the multi-class version of the considered algorithms seems to adapt more to the specificities of both the datasets and the classification tasks. Finally, the results obtained also show the influence of the way audio data is represented. From a more general perspective, it is worth noting that due the simplicity of each algorithm and their proposed improvement, the results obtained on music data in quite ambiguous classification tasks are not satisfying, especially the ones obtained on the *GTZAN* dataset. There still remains a trade-off that needs to be experimentally addressed between the amount of sensitivity and specificity of each outlier detection method. The more specific, the less outliers are likely to be recognized, while the more sensitive the algorithm is, the more inliers are wrongly identified as outliers. The relatively low performance of both outliers detection methods during our subjective evaluation proves that recognizing mislabelled data points in the general context of music classification is still a very challenging task. Throughout this report, we propose more efficient approaches to tackle this problem and demonstrate their impact on generalization.

4.2 Audio Data Augmentation

Data augmentation is a common recourse in order to improve generalization. By increasing the diversity of the data without degrading class distributions, results in [90] show that data augmentation makes the empirical risk $\hat{R}_{aug}(f | \mathcal{P})$ small. Although the consistency between $\hat{R}(f | \mathcal{P})$ and $\hat{R}_{aug}(f | \mathcal{P})$ is not always verified, they claim that data augmentation significantly reduces generalization error. Based on these results and previous work successfully applying augmentation strategies to audio data, we describe here the augmentation policy we propose for the task of music classification.

4.2.1 Data Representation

Mel-spectrograms representations are used as input to the CNN classifiers during training and testing time, as explained in [81]. The number of mel-bands is set to 96 while the frame and hop sizes are equal to 512 and 256 respectively. The data augmentation strategy proposed here will therefore operate on that same representation. It also needs to comply with the two following constraints. First, the transformation process should be computationally cheap in order to be applied "on the fly" while each dataset is being processed before training. Second, the resulting transformations should be complex enough in order to avoid being explicitly learned by the model as described in [35]. We introduce here the data augmentation pipeline that will consist in a series of transformations applied to the original datasets, once each mel-spectrogram has been calculated. We denote by μ and ν the time and frequency dimensions of a mel-spectrogram respectively.

4.2.2 Time-Swapping

The time-swapping transformation proposed in [91] consists in randomly swapping two distinct regions of a given mel-spectrogram along the temporal dimension. More precisely, a block size t is chosen from a uniform distribution from 0 to T . Then, the consecutive time-steps $[t_0, t_0 + t)$ and $[t_1, t_1 + t)$ are swapped, where t_0 and t_1 are

chosen from $[0, \mu - 2t)$ and $[t_0 + t, \mu - t)$, respectively. We denote the number of times the swapping operation is applied by n_{swap} . Intuitively speaking, the time swapping operation moves around some particular temporal patterns present in the input. However, as CNN are translation-invariant, the real advantage of time-swapping is that it creates new sub-regions of the original spectrogram, where for example there is the first half of a verse followed by a sub-part of the chorus. As for the class integrity, even though the swapped mel-spectrogram is chopped between different parts, it is safe to assume that it remains from the same music genre, or belongs to the same mood category.

4.2.3 Frequency-Masking

Frequency masking consists in deleting a certain segment of the mel-spectrogram on the frequency dimension. However, the process followed is relatively similar as time masking. For a given spectrogram S , frequency channels $[f_0, f_0 + f)$ are masked where f is chosen from a uniform distribution from 0 to the frequency mask parameter F , and f_0 is chosen from $(0, v - f)$ where v is the number of frequency channels. Here, we use the implementation proposed in [92]. We denote the number of times the transformation is applied to a given mel-spectrogram S by n_{mask} . The frequency masking transformation aims at limiting how much the model relies on the whole mel-spectrogram. Indeed, if some frequency bands are masked during training, the model will be pushed to extract other types of patterns specific to the given class considered. Here again, the class integrity is preserved once this type of transformation is applied.

4.2.4 Loudness Control

Originally introduced in [93], the loudness control transformation aims at randomly adjusting the loudness value of each input. For a given mel-spectrogram, the algorithm first starts by subtracting its minimum to all components and multiplying them by $1 - \lambda$, where $\lambda \in [0, \Lambda]$. Finally, the minimum is added back to each mel-spectrogram value. The resulting augmented instance has either a softer loudness or

not. This transformation is applied n_{loud} times per mel-spectrogram. The loudness control augmentation plays a crucial role in the augmentation pipeline proposed in this work. The training datasets tend to have varying qualities, where some audio extracts can contain noise or differences in loudness, as observed in 4.1.3. Therefore, loudness control improves how tolerant the model will end up being with regard to loudness differences between songs from a given class.

4.2.5 Random Noise

The last step of the data augmentation pipeline consists in a Gaussian noise addition to the resulting modified mel-spectrogram. In the audio data augmentation literature, Gaussian noise is commonly added to the raw audio waveform before any feature calculation is performed. As our objective is to mimic the noise addition in the temporal domain, it is necessary to take the mel-spectrogram feature calculation into account in order to assess whether adding a Gaussian noise in the time-frequency domain remains faithful to a Gaussian noise in the temporal domain. Let $d[n]$ be a real-valued observation of the original audio signal $x[n]$ and a noise $w[n]$ such that:

$$d[n] = x[n] + w[n] \quad (4.8)$$

We consider that the original signal and the noise are independent. The noise is Gaussian, centered with a stationary variance σ^2 such that $w[n] \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$. Given the linearity of the Fourier transform, we can write the Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) of $d[n]$ as:

$$F_x[n, k] = F_d[n, k] + F_w[n, k] \quad (4.9)$$

From the results of [94], the STFT coefficients $F_w[n, k]$ follow a circular complex Gaussian variable. The spectrogram being the squared modulus of the STFT, we find that each component in the spectrogram of a circular complex Gaussian STFT

will follow a central chi-square distribution with 2 degrees of freedom (as we sum the square of the real and imaginary parts, where they individually follow a centered stationary Gaussian). The scaling parameter $\gamma[n, k]$ is given by the time-varying power spectrum of the noise. Since the noise applied is white, stationary, and if the analysis window is taken such that $\sum_n w^2[n] = 1$, its time-varying power spectrum is a constant (i.e the noise does not depend on the frequency value), equal to σ^2 . Therefore, the final density function of noise-only spectrogram coefficients can be expressed as follows [94]:

$$p_S(s) = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{\sigma^2}\right) \quad (4.10)$$

Note that we also recognize the density of an exponential distribution of parameter $\lambda = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}$. One can also notice that the standard deviation σ^2 of the original noise and λ are inversely proportional. Therefore, the more concentrated around 0 the original noise is, the smaller the magnitude of its impact on the final mel-spectrogram will be. Then, to arrive at a mel-spectrogram representation, the resulting distribution is finally projected onto the Mel-scale using a set of triangular filters. Due to its piece-wise linearity, this operation does not significantly change the overall shape of the chi-square distribution. Finally, in order to estimate the amount of difference between clean and noisy mel-spectrograms, the estimated distribution needs to be mirrored back into the negative side, as the actual noise applied was either positive or negative.

We now experimentally estimate the parameters of the distribution. For a given dataset, we simultaneously calculate the mel-spectrogram of each song, and the mel-spectrogram of the same song with a Gaussian noise added directly on its waveform. For each song we therefore obtain its respective clean and noise mel-spectrograms. Then, we measure the distance between the two mel-spectrograms (component-wise) and estimate the mean $\hat{\mu}$ and the standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}$. Figure 2 shows the distribution of these distances for the happy/not happy dataset. We finally retain $\hat{\mu} \propto 10^{-7}$, $\hat{\sigma} \propto 10^{-6}$ and propose the approximation displayed in Figure 3.

Figure 2: mel-spectrogram Noise Distribution per song (Happy/not Happy dataset).

Figure 3: mel-spectrogram Noise Approximation per song (Happy/not Happy dataset).

Results from Figure 2 were obtained by adding a Gaussian noise of mean 0 and standard deviation equal to 1 to the raw audio waveform of each song in the dataset with an amplitude uniformly sampled from $[0.001, 0.015]$. The parameters of the Fourier transform and the mel-bands extraction are the same as the ones used in [23]. As predicted, we observe that both sides of the experimental noise distribution are curved as exponential distributions. The mean is slightly shifted since the actual noise mean is never exactly 0. The two plots from Figures 2 and 3 were obtained for points belonging to the interval $[\mu_1 - \frac{\sigma_1}{3}, \mu_1 + \frac{\sigma_1}{3}]$, that is to say, close to the mean (representing more than 80% of the total points). It is important to note that

the resulting noise is about 3 orders of magnitude smaller than the average mel-spectrogram coefficient. Therefore, we simply approximate the noise distribution with a Gaussian, using the empirically estimated parameters $\hat{\mu}$ and $\hat{\sigma}$. Note that a large amount of work has been carried out in order to estimate the distribution of noise in time-frequency representations, such as in [95] or [94]. Therefore, the noise estimation proposed here can be greatly improved.

4.2.6 Augmentation Policy

As the next step of the augmentation pipeline, it is necessary to define the way all the different augmentation techniques will be combined and applied one after the other. We refer to this step as the augmentation policy. We list here all the different elements that will be determined by the final augmentation policy:

- **Augmentation parameters:** Each augmentation technique relies on a set of hyperparameters. In order to make the final transformations singular enough, these parameters are randomly sampled from specific intervals of which the bounds are to be determined.
- **Augmentation complexity:** Some transformations can be applied multiple times to a given input in order to increase the amount of distortion of the resulting mel-spectrogram. However, it is possible that applying a given transformation too many times can degrade the useful information related to the class. Therefore, the number of times each transformation is used has to be carefully chosen.
- **Augmentation quantity:** From a given training instance extracted from a training set, it is possible to generate an infinite amount of transformed mel-spectrograms. However, a very large quantity of augmented examples drastically reduces the proportion of original mel-spectrograms in the resulting dataset, which can sometimes lead to poor prediction results. As a consequence, it is also necessary to find a trade-off between improving the model's robustness and preserving the information originally contained in each dataset.

- Augmentation chain: As previously mentioned, one of the constraints the augmentation policy needs to comply with is complexity. To this end, a possible approach is to apply different transformations one after the other. Consequently, it appears mandatory to simultaneously decide which transformations will be applied for a given training example, and the order in which these transformations will be performed.

We carried out several experiments in order to come up with an augmentation policy that improves the results of each model. However, it is certain that this set of parameters is sub-optimal for a number of reasons. First, only a small percentage of all the possible parameters combinations has been tested. Second, each model seems to react differently due to their filter architectures. Third, each dataset comes with its own structure and semantic information. While all the transformations applied in this work do not jeopardize this information individually, there is still a link to be further characterized between how beneficial a given transformation is for a specific classification problem. The order in which the different transformations are operated has also been experimentally tested. However, one can notice that only the order between the noise addition and the loudness control truly matters. Time-swapping and frequency masking can be located anywhere within the augmentation chain. We summarize in Table 8 the different parameters of the data augmentation policy:

Transformation	Parameter	N	Position
Time Swapping	$T \sim \mathcal{U}(\llbracket 100, 200 \rrbracket)$	$n_{swap} \sim \mathcal{U}(\llbracket 0, 10 \rrbracket)$	1
Frequency Masking	$F \sim \mathcal{U}(\llbracket 2, 10 \rrbracket)$	$n_{mask} \sim \mathcal{U}(\llbracket 2, 5 \rrbracket)$	3
Loudness Control	$\Lambda = 1$	$n_{loud} = 1$	2
Noise Addition	$\mu \propto 10^{-7}, \sigma \propto 10^{-6}$	$n_{noise} = 1$	4

Table 8: Augmentation Policy, where N corresponds to the number of times each transformation is applied, and position refers to their overall position within the chaining strategy.

In order to maintain a high degree of diversity among the augmented data points, we also uniformly sample the number of transformations that will be applied to a given song from $\{2, 3, 4\}$. This process is repeated three times, which results in a three time greater training dataset. Higher augmentation has proven to be detrimental to

the learning process, as the proportion of original songs is far too small compared to augmented instances.

4.2.7 Results

Results reported in Tables 9 and 10 show a relatively low improvement over the baseline when the proposed data augmentation policy is applied only on the training set. It is important to note that the purpose of these results is to highlight the potential of audio data augmentation applied directly into the feature space. The augmentation policy proposed is far from being optimized for each specific classification task and its corresponding dataset, as witnessed with the poor results obtained for the Genre classification tasks. Further improvements can potentially be made using a more precise hyperparameters tuning step. More complex transformations such as spectrogram-based time warping can also increase the diversity of the resulting transformed data points which could ultimately improve the generalization capacities of both models.

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.61 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.03	0.42	0.44
genre-gtzan	0.88 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.02	0.46	0.46
genre-rosamerica	0.95 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01	0.51	0.50
mood-acoustic	0.95 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.04	0.68	0.70
mood-electronic	0.93 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.02	0.72	0.75
mood-aggressive	0.97 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.03	0.67	0.69
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.03	0.64	0.69
mood-happy	0.86 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.04	0.59	0.60
mood-sad	0.89 ± 0.04	0.92 ± 0.03	0.65	0.63
mood-party	0.92 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.04	0.73	0.73
danceability	0.96 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.64	0.66
voice/instrumental	0.99 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	0.80	0.79
gender	0.60 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.03	0.77	0.77
timbre	0.91 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.02	0.61	0.63
tonal/atonal	0.88 ± 0.18	0.98 ± 0.01	0.62	0.62

Table 9: Data augmentation influence on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.48 ± 0.27	0.50 ± 0.02	0.40	0.37
genre-gtzan	0.80 ± 0.23	0.81 ± 0.01	0.43	0.40
genre-rosamerica	0.81 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.02	0.46	0.43
mood-acoustic	0.94 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.03	0.70	0.71
mood-electronic	0.88 ± 0.39	0.89 ± 0.05	0.75	0.70
mood-aggressive	0.96 ± 0.11	0.97 ± 0.02	0.70	0.72
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.30	0.88 ± 0.03	0.67	0.68
mood-happy	0.79 ± 0.05	0.84 ± 0.04	0.57	0.61
mood-sad	0.87 ± 0.22	0.89 ± 0.03	0.62	0.63
mood-party	0.91 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.05	0.72	0.71
danceability	0.93 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.04	0.69	0.68
voice/instrumental	0.93 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.03	0.77	0.77
gender	0.58 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.04	0.74	0.75
timbre	0.84 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.04	0.54	0.56
tonal/atonal	0.95 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.03	0.58	0.59

Table 10: Data augmentation influence on the VGG transfer learning model.

4.2.8 Conclusion

Audio data augmentation seems to be an efficient way to improve the general capacity of deep learning music classifiers. Despite the simplicity of each individual transformation, the proposed chaining strategy manages to increase the performance of both models on most of the classification tasks. There seems to be a relationship between the filters' shape of each architecture and the task benefiting from data augmentation. For the MusiCNN model, performance with data augmentation on any classification task is either very close or above the baseline. With both horizontal and vertical filters [83], the MusiCNN model is more impacted by audio transformations such as frequency masking or time swapping. Implicitly, the model is pushed not to rely on less important characteristics of the input that are distorted by data augmentation, such as very long temporal dependencies or individual pitches. As for the VGG model, its small squared filters will solely focus on short time-frequency patterns. Therefore, frequency masking will locally impact the filtering operations while time swapping will relocate the response to the same filter in the time-frequency representation and create new transitions among

non-consecutive chunks. Future work seems to be needed in order to establish the connection between transformations applied in the audio domain, their approximation in the time-frequency domain and their direct impact on CNNs. The high specificity of each dataset also implies the need for adaptive augmentation policies, which could for example be learned through a meta learning-based algorithm. The main idea of such an algorithm would be, given a dataset and a set of labels, to find discriminating and non-discriminating features and adapt the augmentation policy accordingly with the objective of maximizing the evaluation performance of the model and improve domain adaptation. When the transformations carefully applied coincide with labels' meaning, audio data augmentation can be an implicit way of introducing expert knowledge about a given task. By distorting non pertinent attributes of the data, it is possible to enforce the model to learn relevant features, more likely to be generalizable.

Chapter 5

Noise Robustness

Training machine learning models on datasets with label noise can limit the amount of information they extract, and even drive them towards skewed distribution approximations. Neural networks have proven to be powerful enough to memorize the noise contained in the data [96], which makes their training process less efficient and reduces their final generalization capacities. We have previously shown how outliers detection algorithms can help alleviate this issue by spotting and possibly discarding corrupted data points before training. However, we have also seen that these methods suffer from a high dependency to the task addressed and a careful parameters tuning step. Another type of noise that we hope to address is the ambiguity present among labels for some classification tasks. In this chapter, we propose to approach these two issues from a different perspective. We explore two main strategies that aim to make deep learning models more robust to noisy labels while modelling the perceptual ambiguity that can be encountered in some classification tasks.

5.1 Label Smoothing

Label smoothing aims at modifying the initial targets the model is given in order to regulate its optimization process during training. Usually, label smoothing is used as a way to combat overfitting by constraining the model not to learn hard probabilities. In case of noisy data, label smoothing helps limiting the influence of

noise onto the training process. However, we also hope for this strategy to be a way to algorithmically represent how ambiguous certain classification tasks can be.

5.1.1 Uniform Smoothing

Description

The first label smoothing strategy we propose to explore corresponds to a uniform smoothing. As previously described, given a K -class classification problem, uniform label smoothing operates by combining hard binary labels and a uniform distribution over the different classes. More specifically, we can formulate the process as follows [44]: we write the predictions of a neural network based on its penultimate layer as $p_k = \frac{e^{\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{w}_k}}{\sum_{l=1}^L e^{\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{w}_l}}$ where p_k denotes the likelihood the model assigns to the k th class, \mathbf{w}_k the weights and biases of the last layer and \mathbf{x} the activations of the penultimate layer of the network. If this same network is trained on hard labels (i.e binary), then it aims at minimizing the cross-entropy between the true labels y_k and its output p_k as in $H(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{k=1}^K -y_k \log(p_k)$. Given a parameter α , label smoothing modifies the targets y_k such that $y_k^{LS} = y_k(1 - \alpha) + \frac{\alpha}{K}$. The labels modification implied by uniform label smoothing is neither dependent on each specific class, nor each specific training instance. In order to assess whether this approach alleviates the two aforementioned problems that are label noise and label ambiguity, we perform a series of experiments where we apply uniform smoothing while fine-tuning both the pre-trained VGG and MusiCNN models on each classification task. Additionally, we try to measure the influence of the smoothing strength denoted by the hyperparameter α . To this end, we report the 5-fold cross-validation results on each training sets for both architectures, and their performance on the MTG-Jamendo dataset, for optimal values of α .

Results

As described in Tables 11 and 12, label smoothing tends to slightly improve generalization results in most classification tasks for both models. More specifically, the most straightforward tasks seem to benefit the most from smoothing, as opposed

to most subjective ones such as Happy, Sad or Party. Additionally, there does not seem to be a consistent correlation between the generalization improvement or deterioration and the performance of the model on the training set. In some cases such as for Genre-Dortmund, Relaxed or Gender, training performance is reduced while results on the MTG-Jamendo dataset are improved. On the contrary, a higher training performance can sometimes lead to a higher generalization capacity such as for the Genre-Rosamerica or the Electronic classification tasks. This absence of link between training and testing performances can imply that the learning process of each model is not affected by the smoothing operation. However, generalization results show that smoothing labels pushes the model to extract and learn another kind of information from the training datasets which results in a better robustness against mislabelled data points and class ambiguity.

Dataset	Smoothing	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.1	0.61 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.02	0.42	0.44
genre-gtzan	0.1	0.88 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.02	0.46	0.46
genre-rosamerica	0.1	0.95 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01	0.51	0.54
mood-acoustic	0.2	0.95 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.68	0.69
mood-electronic	0.3	0.93 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.02	0.72	0.75
mood-aggressive	0.1	0.97 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.02	0.67	0.68
mood-relaxed	0.2	0.89 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.02	0.64	0.68
mood-happy	0.3	0.86 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.02	0.59	0.60
mood-sad	0.2	0.89 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.03	0.65	0.65
mood-party	0.1	0.92 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.03	0.73	0.73
danceability	0.3	0.96 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.64	0.65
voice/instrumental	0.2	0.99 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	0.80	0.80
gender	0.3	0.60 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.02	0.77	0.79
timbre	0.1	0.91 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.01	0.61	0.59
tonal/atonal	0.2	0.88 ± 0.18	0.98 ± 0.01	0.62	0.62

Table 11: Uniform smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

5.1.2 Label Distribution Learning

The uniform approach has shown to be effective in some particular cases, except where there is a significant perceptual ambiguity among labels. However, applying the same amount of smoothing to all data points remains a gross approximation

Dataset	Smoothing	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.3	0.48 ± 0.27	0.45 ± 0.01	0.40	0.41
genre-gtzan	0.1	0.80 ± 0.23	0.80 ± 0.01	0.43	0.43
genre-rosamerica	0.2	0.91 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.46	0.59
mood-acoustic	0.3	0.94 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.03	0.70	0.69
mood-electronic	0.3	0.88 ± 0.39	0.89 ± 0.05	0.75	0.76
mood-aggressive	0.1	0.96 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.01	0.70	0.72
mood-relaxed	0.1	0.89 ± 0.30	0.87 ± 0.08	0.67	0.68
mood-happy	0.1	0.79 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.02	0.57	0.57
mood-sad	0.1	0.87 ± 0.22	0.90 ± 0.02	0.62	0.63
mood-party	0.2	0.91 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.04	0.72	0.72
danceability	0.2	0.93 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.03	0.69	0.69
voice/instrumental	0.2	0.93 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	0.77	0.77
gender	0.3	0.58 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.02	0.74	0.75
timbre	0.2	0.84 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.02	0.54	0.56
tonal/atonal	0.1	0.95 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.03	0.58	0.58

Table 12: Uniform smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.

of each classification task’s specificities. Although the training datasets are only composed of a few hundred instances, there exists a variability in each data point’s class ambiguity. Intuitively, it would seem relevant to make the smoothing amount dependent on each training instance’s relative position between classes. Therefore, we propose an extension of this approach by introducing further information about each dataset’s topology. The fundamental idea is the following: the more ambiguous a data point is, the smoother (i.e continuous) its labels should be. On the contrary, the more anchored a training sample is in its class, then the harder (i.e close to binary) its labels are. Another way to view this problem is to express each label’s value as the proportion of the input that is explained by this specific label. From a musical point of view, this assumption means that an audio extract that is perceptually close to the decision boundary between classes should be represented by a smoother combination of these classes. Algorithmically speaking, the classification problem can be reformulated as a labels distribution prediction, also commonly referred as Label Distribution Learning (LDL) [97]:

Label Distribution Learning: Let $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{R}^n$ denote the input space and $\mathcal{Y} = \{y_i\}_{i=1}^K$ denote the complete set of labels. Given a training set $S = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, the goal of LDL is to learn a conditional probability mass function $p(y | \mathbf{x})$ from S , where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ and $y \in \mathcal{Y}$.

Instead of predicting binary (i.e hard) labels, LDL aims at approximating multiple real-valued description degrees of the labels. Therefore, to convert the original classification task to a LDL problem, it is necessary to transform the label vectors of each training instance. This label modification process, also known as Label Enhancement (LE) can be formally defined as follows [98]: let $\mathbf{y}_i \in \{0; 1\}^K$ be the original label vector of $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}$ where K denotes the total number of classes. LE recovers the label distribution \mathbf{d}_i of \mathbf{x}_i from \mathbf{y}_i such that $\mathbf{d}_i \in [0; 1]^K$ and $\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{d}_i^k = 1$. Then, the final training set becomes $S = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{d}_i) | 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. Leveraging information extracted from the dataset to enhance labels involves complying with three important assumptions [99]:

- Continuity: data points close to each other in the feature space are likely to share a label. Although this assumption depends highly on the audio features that are being considered, audio extracts that have similar features, are usually expected to belong to the same class.
- Cluster: the data is composed of different clusters wherein data points are likely to share a label. Perceptually speaking, classes can be composed of several sub-groups which share the same label. If we take the example of music genre classification, then a class could be "Rock" songs, while sub-groups could be "Indie", "Punk" or "Progressive Rock". For mood classification, these sub-groups can also correspond to mid-level features such as pitch and beat-related information. Again, this assumption relies heavily on the set of audio features that are extracted beforehand. The structure of the feature space will therefore not always be built upon the same kind of groups of instances.
- Manifold: the data is spread along a lower dimensional manifold. Despite the high dimensionality of audio data, is it reasonable to assume that for a given

classification task, an underlying mapping of the data separates more clearly the different classes.

We propose to look at three basic approaches that aim at leveraging information from datasets in order to approximate new targets that will serve as label distributions, specific to each training instance. We also show that applying a linear transformation supervised by label information before enhancing labels further improves the efficiency of smoothing. In our context, as we deal with datasets having a varying degree of ambiguity in their labels, there is a risk that the LE step switches some training instances from their original class to a different one. In order to simultaneously preserve the integrity of the dataset while having a more accurate representation of the target distribution among training instances, the new targets will be calculated as a linear combination of both the smooth and hard original labels as follows: for each training instance \mathbf{x}_i , we first convert its hard binary label y_i into a one-hot vector $\mathbf{y}_i^{old} \in \{0, 1\}^K$, where K is the total number of classes. Then, let $\mathbf{d}_i \in \mathbb{R}^K$ denote the new smooth label vector obtained after the LE step. The final label distribution \mathbf{y}_i^{new} of \mathbf{x}_i will be given by:

$$\mathbf{y}_i^{new} = \alpha \times \mathbf{y}_i^{old} + (1 - \alpha) \times \mathbf{d}_i \quad (5.1)$$

where $\alpha \in [0; 1]$. As witnessed throughout the outlier detection chapter, distance measurements in the feature space are not always perceptually relevant. Therefore, the objective of this final label combination is to avoid any accidental label flipping, while smoothing as much as possible training instances that are the most ambiguous, and preserving harder labels for data points that are well rooted in the topological structure of their originally assigned class. Finally, the LDL paradigm shifts the original classification problem towards a regression problem, where new targets to be predicted are continuous values ranging from 0 to 1. In the following experiments, we use the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) loss function due to its robustness against label noise. In the following experiments, we use $\alpha = 0.5$ to balance between the original and new targets.

5.1.3 Local Smoothing

Description

It is possible for existing algorithms to be adapted to the LE task. As described in [97], the k -nearest neighbours (k-NN) algorithm can be modified in order to approximate the labels distribution of a given instance \mathbf{x} . First, by assuming that the feature space can be represented by a graph \mathcal{G} , the k nearest neighbours of \mathbf{x} are selected. Then, its labels distribution is approximated by the average labels distributions of its neighbours as follows:

$$p(y_j | \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i \in N_k(\mathbf{x})} y_j^i, (j = 1, 2, \dots, K) \quad (5.2)$$

where $N_k(\mathbf{x})$ is the index set of the k nearest neighbors of \mathbf{x} in the training set. In our context, the variable \mathbf{x} will iterate over all the training instances of each dataset. We use a fixed number of neighbours $k = 10$. We also choose not to propagate the newly smoothed labels throughout the algorithm to avoid spreading any smoothing error.

Results

As a first attempt towards an adaptive smoothing method, the local approach tends to have a varying effect based on the model architecture employed. From a general perspective, it is clear that the improvements over the baselines are not as consistent as for uniform smoothing. In cases where the k-NN approach ameliorates the generalization performance, it usually outperforms the improvements brought by uniform smoothing. As a consequence, it is safe to assume that introducing topological information into the smoothing process can further improve the models generalization capacities. However, the performance on the majority of the classification tasks is deteriorated. These poor results can be potentially explained by the simplicity of the approach, which does not take into account the relative distances among neighbours. Therefore, a data point that is greatly isolated within the feature space will

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.61 ± 0.02	0.54 ± 0.02	0.42	0.43
genre-gtzan	0.88 ± 0.01	0.87 ± 0.02	0.46	0.40
genre-rosamerica	0.95 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.03	0.51	0.53
mood-acoustic	0.95 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.68	0.70
mood-electronic	0.93 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.05	0.72	0.76
mood-aggressive	0.97 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	0.67	0.62
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.02	0.64	0.69
mood-happy	0.86 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.03	0.59	0.59
mood-sad	0.89 ± 0.04	0.86 ± 0.05	0.65	0.62
mood-party	0.92 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.05	0.73	0.72
danceability	0.96 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.64	0.66
voice/instrumental	0.99 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01	0.80	0.79
gender	0.60 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.02	0.77	0.78
timbre	0.91 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.01	0.61	0.60
tonal/atonal	0.88 ± 0.18	0.78 ± 0.04	0.62	0.66

Table 13: Local smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

still inherit the label information of its neighbours, even if they are relatively far away from it. Second, the averaged MFCC features might be accountable for the loss of valuable temporal information. Additionally, the resulting topological space does not necessarily translate the semantic distance among the different songs, which in case of very high level classification tasks, can end up in a semantically irrelevant smoothing. Finally, adaptive smoothing methods only significantly affect the labels of a handful of data points. If actual ambiguous or mislabelled points are not surrounded by points from distinct classes, then their label distribution will remain the same. On the contrary, the uniform smoothing method is applied to all data points regardless of their location in the feature space. This way, all noisy or mislabelled points have their label distribution modified regardless of their position within the feature space.

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.48 ± 0.27	0.40±0.03	0.40	0.37
genre-gtzan	0.80 ± 0.23	0.77 ± 0.03	0.43	0.38
genre-rosamerica	0.81 ± 0.02	0.87±0.04	0.46	0.58
mood-acoustic	0.94 ± 0.01	0.89±0.04	0.70	0.68
mood-electronic	0.88 ± 0.39	0.84 ± 0.07	0.75	0.73
mood-aggressive	0.96 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.01	0.70	0.62
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.30	0.91 ± 0.02	0.67	0.65
mood-happy	0.79 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.01	0.57	0.58
mood-sad	0.87 ± 0.22	0.86 ± 0.05	0.62	0.62
mood-party	0.91 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	0.72	0.69
danceability	0.93 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.02	0.69	0.69
voice/instrumental	0.93 ± 0.02	0.87±0.05	0.77	0.73
gender	0.58 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.02	0.74	0.76
timbre	0.84 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.02	0.54	0.61
tonal/atonal	0.95 ± 0.03	0.70±0.04	0.58	0.54

Table 14: Local smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.

5.1.4 Weighted Smoothing

Description

We propose an extension of the previous k -NN based approach by introducing extra information about the topology of the feature space. As described in [100], it is assumed again that the structure of this space can be represented by a graph \mathcal{G} . Let \mathbf{W} be the matrix of which the elements $w_{i,j}$ represent the strength of the relationship between \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j . If we assume that all points lie on local linear manifolds, then each of them can be expressed as a linear combination of its k nearest neighbours, the manifold approximation problem can then be formulated as a minimization of the following expression:

$$\Theta(\mathbf{W}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\| \mathbf{x}_i - \sum_{j \neq i} w_{i,j} \mathbf{x}_j \right\|^2 \quad (5.3)$$

under the following constraint:

$$\sum_{j \neq i} w_{i,j} = 1, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (5.4)$$

where $w_{i,j} = 0$ except if \mathbf{x}_j belongs to the k nearest neighbours of \mathbf{x}_i . This approximation can be solved by the following n least-square programming problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{W}_i} \quad & \mathbf{W}_i^T \mathbf{G}_i \mathbf{W}_i \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{1}^T \mathbf{W}_i = 1, \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

where \mathbf{G}_i is the Gram matrix at point x_i such that $\mathbf{G}_i^{jk} = (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)^T (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_k)$. This least square programming optimization problem is conveniently solvable. The magnitude of each coefficient $w_{i,j}$ is then normalized so that $\sum_{j \neq i} |w_{i,j}| = 1, 1 \leq i \leq n$. Unlike the simple k -NN based approach previously seen, the goal here is to determine how much each neighbour \mathbf{x}_j accounts for the reconstruction of \mathbf{x}_i in order to design a hierarchy among neighbours during the label distribution approximation. Finally, according to the continuity assumption previously stated, the structure of the feature space is transferred to the label space. Therefore, the weights $w_{i,j}$ determined for each point \mathbf{x}_i are used to retrieve the projected vectors \mathbf{d}_i that minimize the global cost function:

$$\Theta_2(D) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left\| \mathbf{d}_i - \sum_{j \neq i} w_{i,j} \mathbf{y}_j \right\|^2 \quad (5.6)$$

To summarize, as the feature and label spaces optimize these linear forms, the local neighborhoods within these spaces have the same properties. As a consequence, the label distribution \mathbf{d}_i of \mathbf{x}_i can be approximated by a weighted linear combination of the nearest neighbours' label distributions of \mathbf{x}_i . In our experiments, we adapt the original method proposed in [101] of the Locally Linear Embedding (LLE) as detailed in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Manifold Learning Algorithm

```

W  $\in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ ;
 $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} = \{(x_i, y_i) \mid 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ ;
for  $x_i \in \mathcal{X}$  do
    create a matrix  $Z$  with all neighbors of  $x_i$ ;
    subtract  $x_i$  from  $Z$ ;
    create the local covariance matrix  $C = ZZ^T$ ;
    add a regularizing term to avoid  $C$  being singular,  $C = C + \text{reg} \times I$ ;
    solve  $C\mathbf{W} = 1$  for  $\mathbf{W}$ ;
    set  $w_{i,j} = 0$  if  $x_j$  is not a neighbor of  $x_i$ ;
    set  $\mathbf{W} = |\mathbf{W}| / \text{sum}(|\mathbf{W}|)$ ;
    for  $k = 1 \dots K$  do
        | set  $d_{i,k} = \sum_{j \neq i} w_{i,j} y_{j,k}$ ;
    end
end

```

Results

As the k-NN approach, the weighted smoothing strategy gives mixed results between both models. First, it seems that the weighting strategy among neighbours is detrimental to the learning process of the MusiCNN model. Only 5 classification tasks have improved over the baseline, against 8 when using the k-NN approach. On the contrary, the VGG model seems to react better to the weighted smoothing. First, its performance on 6 classification tasks has improved over the baseline, compared to 4 for the k-NN smoothing. Second, the average classification score is substantially higher than for the k-NN approach. The boost in performance using the weighted smoothing is also sparser than using the uniform approach. As previously mentioned, this form of targeted smoothing eventually modifies the label distributions of a handful of data points, while the uniform approach is applied to all training instances. In the case where the weighted approach fails at spotting an abnormal data point, then its final smooth label will remain the same. It is also possible that some highly dense regions of each dataset contain outliers. In this case, operating a weighting operation in the final label distribution calculation can be detrimental, as the algorithm will pay less attention to the overall location of this highly dense region of outliers. However, it is worth noting that each improvement over the baseline brought by the weighted smoothing are higher than the ones from

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.61 ± 0.02	0.52±0.02	0.42	0.42
genre-gtzan	0.88 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.02	0.46	0.45
genre-rosamerica	0.95 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01	0.51	0.51
mood-acoustic	0.95 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.68	0.69
mood-electronic	0.93 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.04	0.72	0.76
mood-aggressive	0.97 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.01	0.67	0.62
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.02	0.64	0.68
mood-happy	0.86 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.05	0.59	0.59
mood-sad	0.89 ± 0.04	0.83±0.05	0.65	0.64
mood-party	0.92 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.05	0.73	0.73
danceability	0.96 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.04	0.64	0.65
voice/instrumental	0.99 ± 0.01	0.94±0.01	0.80	0.78
gender	0.60 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.01	0.77	0.79
timbre	0.91 ± 0.01	0.87±0.02	0.61	0.59
tonal/atonal	0.88 ± 0.18	0.79 ± 0.04	0.62	0.58

Table 15: Weighted smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

the uniform approach, which still confirms our general assumption that leveraging the topological information of each dataset enriches the label smoothing process.

5.1.5 Semantic-Aware Smoothing

Motivations

Our previous experiments following different label smoothing strategies show that adaptive smoothing methods tend to outperform the uniform approach. These results confirm the assumption that taking the amount of ambiguity of each song into consideration can improve the generalization capacity of a classifier. However, different listening evaluations have highlighted some inconsistency in the label modification process, where some songs would be shifted out of their original class without any perceptual justification. As previously described, the label enhancement process relies on several constraints. The lack of stability of the two previous adaptive smoothing strategies can therefore be explained by the fact that some of these constraints are violated in the feature space considered. For example, Figures 4 and 5 show a 2-dimensional t-SNE projection of the GTZAN and "Relaxed"

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.48 ± 0.27	0.43 ± 0.01	0.40	0.45
genre-gtzan	0.80 ± 0.23	0.79 ± 0.02	0.43	0.42
genre-rosamerica	0.81 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.01	0.46	0.63
mood-acoustic	0.94 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.03	0.70	0.70
mood-electronic	0.88 ± 0.39	0.86 ± 0.06	0.75	0.75
mood-aggressive	0.96 ± 0.11	0.94 ± 0.02	0.70	0.68
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.30	0.90 ± 0.02	0.67	0.69
mood-happy	0.79 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.04	0.57	0.58
mood-sad	0.87 ± 0.22	0.87 ± 0.06	0.62	0.62
mood-party	0.91 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.03	0.72	0.72
danceability	0.93 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.04	0.69	0.68
voice/instrumental	0.93 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.03	0.77	0.76
gender	0.58 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.02	0.74	0.77
timbre	0.84 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.01	0.54	0.59
tonal/atonal	0.95 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.05	0.58	0.51

Table 16: Weighted smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.

datasets respectively. It is clear that both the continuity and cluster constraints are not respected, as points from similar classes tend to be spread over the whole feature space without any clear grouping. This inevitably results in a loss of class semantic information once label smoothing algorithms are applied. Ideally, one would want to apply these methods in a space that inherently captures the actual meaning of each class, where the location of each data point would truly represent its relative perceptual position with regard to the different classes observed. In other words, we wish to look for a low-dimensional space in which songs belonging to the same class should be close to each other, given a certain distance metric, while songs from distinct classes should be pushed apart. Moreover, this ideal space should also remain faithful to the potential ambiguity that comes with each song, by placing very ambiguous songs in-between the different groups of data points corresponding to each class. To summarize, a semantic-aware space should represent:

- Class-semantic information: data points from different classes should form distinguishable clusters.
- Individual ambiguity: each data point’s location within this space should be

consistent with its perceptual position between each class.

Approach

The search for a semantically relevant space is a problem that can be addressed with various angles. A possible strategy is to look for a transformation that can be applied to all data points from a given dataset, where the resulting coordinates of each point comply with the aforementioned constraints related to class information. It is also possible to determine another distance metric which will render the class information among the data points. In this work, given the small size of the datasets considered, we propose a simple yet powerful approach based on Distance Metric Learning (DML) [102]:

Distance Metric Learning: *Given an input distance function $d(x, y)$ between objects x and y (for example, the Euclidean distance), along with supervised information regarding an ideal distance, Distance Metric Learning either aims at constructing a new distance function $\tilde{d}(x, y)$ which is “better” than the original distance function for a particular task, or learning a transformation function f so that the original distance function $d(x, y)$ can be used over the mapped data $d(f(x, y))$.*

Of all the numerous methods that have been proposed to solve the problem of DML, we choose to constrain our work on linear methods. If we consider the Euclidean distance, i.e $d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|_2$, as the input distance function, the goal here is to learn a linear mapping encoded by a matrix G such that the learned distance is $\tilde{d}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \|G\mathbf{x} - G\mathbf{y}\|_2$. In order to learn a relevant distance metric for the task of label smoothing, the DML method needs to be provided with supervised information. In our case, we propose to use label information as supervision for the DML algorithm. This way, the learned distance metric (or linear transformation) might hopefully result in a space that complies with the two constraints stated in 5.1.5. This final space, due to its low dimensionality and by giving more perceptual meaning to the euclidean distance, enables us to finally apply the local smoothing approach.

Figure 4: 2-D t-SNE projection of the GTZAN Dataset (Averaged MFCC features).

Figure 5: 2-D t-SNE projection of the "Relaxed" Dataset (Averaged MFCC features).

Method

Besides employing a DML algorithm, we also propose to leverage further information about each training instance by using the whole MFCC features as input. This way, it is possible to include some temporal information that was previously lost by averaging each MFCC coefficient. Previous experiments have shown that this extra information can be beneficial in this context, as the same smoothing method directly applied to averaged MFCC representations did not perform as well as when using them entirely. We first start by applying a non-linear Principal Component Analysis (PCA) using an Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel [103] for two main reasons: we wish to reduce the dimensionality of the input and, given the inconsistent results of the two previous linear smoothing strategies, we try to introduce a non-linear operation into the pipeline. Then, we propose to employ the Large Margin Nearest Neighbor (LMNN) algorithm originally proposed in [104]. The main idea of LMNN is to learn a metric distance (i.e a linear transformation) in a k-NN classification setting, where the said metric tries to keep close k-nearest neighbours of the same class, while pushing examples from distinct classes apart. The main advantage of this method is that it does not make any assumption about the distribution of the data. Additionally, as it tries to optimize performance of k-NN based approaches, the final distance metric will fit the smoothing algorithm later applied. The transformation (i.e distance metric) is learned by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\min_{A \geq 0} (1 - \lambda) \underbrace{\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{S}} d_A(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)}_{\text{Pull}} + \lambda \underbrace{\sum_{(i,j,k) \in \mathcal{R}} [1 + d_A(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) - d_A(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_k)]_+}_{\text{Push}} \quad (5.7)$$

where A is some positive semi-definite matrix denoting the learned linear transformation, \mathcal{S} is the set of pairs composed of \mathbf{x}_i and its k-nearest neighbors of the same class, \mathcal{R} is defined as a set of triples (i, j, k) such that \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j share the same label while \mathbf{x}_k is a data point with a different label within the same region. Finally, $[\cdot]_+ = \max(0, \cdot)$ corresponds to the Hinge loss and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ is a weighting parameter that balances the two objectives. If $\lambda = 0$, then the algorithm only focuses

on bringing nearest neighbors of the same class close, whereas if $\lambda = 1$, it only pushes away data points from distinct classes. These two objectives are described in Figure 6 where the term *target neighbor* refers to a point that should be similar to \mathbf{x}_i while *impostor* is one of its nearest neighbors with a different label. We use the implementation of the LMNN algorithm from [105].

Figure 6: Objectives of the LMNN algorithm, adapted from [104].

The overall pipeline followed here requires a number of decisions to be made regarding hyperparameter values of the different algorithms employed. We feed as input a flattened version of MFCC features: we denote by $S \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times T}$ the MFCC matrix of a given song, where T is the number of time frames and K the number of MFCC coefficients. In order to use as much information from MFCCs as possible, we convert them to a vector representation $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^L$ where $L = KT$. Given the high dimensionality of the input (several thousand components), a first parameter to decide on is the number of principal components from the non linear PCA used, which we refer to as N_{PCA} . Second, it is necessary to define the dimensionality N_{ML} of the linear embedding determined by the LMNN algorithm. Here, it is to be noted that the Euclidean distance will further be applied to the transformed data, therefore, we look for relatively low values for N_{ML} in order for the Euclidean distance to be as relevant as possible. Finally, the balance parameter λ and the number of neighbors k of the LMNN algorithm have to be fixed beforehand. Various experiments have been carried out in order to determine what seem to be optimal values for these

parameters that we describe in Table 17. In order to evaluate the quality of each parameter values combination without having to train both classifiers, we looked at the number of points that were shifted from their original class to a different one after applying the local label smoothing algorithm. As a result, the more semantically relevant the output space of the LMNN algorithm is, the less data points were re-labelled as belonging to a different class (because we deal with relatively low label noise rates η). For the sake of simplicity, we ended up choosing the same set of parameter values for each datasets sub-category: Genre, Mood and Miscellaneous.

Datasets	N_{PCA}	N_{ML}	λ	k
Genre	256	64	0.5	3
Mood	64	32	0.05	3
Miscellaneous	64	32	0.05	3

Table 17: Semantic-Aware smoothing hyperparameter values.

Each of the parameters described here plays a role in the way the dataset information is summarized and transformed. First, the smaller the N_{PCA} parameter is, the more generic the output representation is, which on the one hand, logically reduces the resulting smoothing sensitivity by discarding noise from the data, and on the other hand, as the PCA algorithm does not take class information into account, results in blurrier class clusters. The same conclusion arises regarding the parameter N_{ML} , where smaller values yield less distinguishable data clusters. There also seems to be a high dependency between the complexity of each dataset (i.e number and separability of classes) and the quality of the LMNN algorithm’s output space. The λ parameter plays an important role in pushing the algorithm towards the desired behaviour. For example in Genre classification tasks, as the optimization problem is complex, we want the different classes to be separated as much as possible. However for the rest of the datasets, we choose to mainly focus on pulling similarly labelled data points together without necessarily taking points from other classes into account. This modified objective enables the algorithm to sometimes place data points from different classes close to each other, which gives sense to the smoothing algorithm applied afterwards. Finally, the number of neighbors k of the LMNN method is kept relatively low given the possible presence of mislabelled instances

in each dataset. As a consequence, outliers' influence on the overall optimization process and the resulting transformed space can be reduced. To verify the efficiency of this procedure, we vary the number of neighbours k_s used by the local smoothing method. It is worth taking into account that the closer k_s is to k , the less sensitive the smoothing will be. Similarly, the further apart k_s and k are, the stronger the resulting smoothing will be. We experiment with different values of k_s and report the results obtained in Tables 18 and 19.

Results

A preliminary evaluation of the proposed method is to look at a projection onto the new low dimensional space of each dataset and their respective classes. As shown in Figures 7 and 8 for the GTZAN and "Relaxed" datasets respectively, we can see that all classes seem to be overall better separated than in the original feature space. For the GTZAN dataset specifically, it is interesting to see that the Metal and Classical categories are located on opposite sides of the new space, which intuitively complies with their high perceptual dissimilarity. Although the Classical category is quite isolated from the rest of the dataset, its nearest class is Jazz, which could potentially be justified by the instruments they share in their typical musical ensemble. A same observation can be made on the lower part of the graph, where Metal is located close to Rock and some Blues tracks. As for the "Relaxed" dataset, even though its original structural organization was already showing some separation among classes, the metric learning method has improved how distinct this separation appears, while still preserving some tracks located either "in-between" classes or completely shifted outside of their original category. Throughout our experiments, we also noticed that within a given dataset category such as Mood, some datasets tend to be easily separable by our proposed method, while others remain fuzzy with data points from each class being scattered all around the new calculated space. For example, the Aggressive dataset shows two clear clusters of data points representing each class, which is probably due to the apparent acoustic dissimilarity among the classes. On the contrary, datasets such as Electronic do not give very clear classes, as songs using electronic instruments can have very diverse

acoustic attributes and result in a less optimal solution for the LMNN algorithm. However, when applying a simple k-NN classifier on any transformed dataset, the results obtained are constantly improved than when performed in the original feature space.

Figure 7: 2-D t-SNE projection of the GTZAN Dataset (PCA & LMNN).

The notion of perceptual proximity and distance among songs is directly dependent on the nature of the classification task that is being addressed. The goal of the proposed method was to transform each dataset so that the position of each song accounts for its perceptual location among the different classes considered. As evidenced by the results reported in Tables 18 and 19, this way of leveraging class information when projecting data onto a lower dimensional space seems to be efficient. The new topological structure of each transformed dataset appears to be faithful to the perceptual closeness among songs, given the nature of the classification task. Our proposed projection followed by the k-NN-based smoothing algorithm, almost always outperforms the baseline without requiring any specific parameters tuning. These results make this last smoothing strategy way more consistent than any other

Figure 8: 2-D t-SNE projection of the "Relaxed" Dataset (PCA & LMNN).

ones previously described in this work. However, as each dataset comes with its own level of ambiguity, the proposed semantic smoothing has the potential to bring even higher improvements with further tuning of the parameters described in Table 17. It is also worth noting that for some particular datasets such as tonal/atonal, the proposed low dimensional space tends to have a negative effect on the generalization capacity of the classifiers. In this particular case, we assume that this loss of generalization is due to the low ambiguity carried by the task, which makes the original feature space already convenient to apply smoothing on.

5.1.6 Conclusion

Several experiments have been performed in order to assess the capacity of label smoothing to help deep learning classifiers to cope with label noise and possible ambiguity among classes. Overall, label smoothing has provided consistent improvements over the different classification tasks. The uniform approach, by its simplicity, is an quite an easy way to estimate how much the learning process can be improved

Dataset	k_s	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	10	0.61 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.01	0.42	0.44
genre-gtzan	10	0.88 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.02	0.46	0.46
genre-rosamerica	10	0.95 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.01	0.51	0.52
mood-acoustic	30	0.95 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.68	0.71
mood-electronic	15	0.93 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.03	0.72	0.77
mood-aggressive	10	0.97 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.01	0.67	0.68
mood-relaxed	25	0.89 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.03	0.64	0.69
mood-happy	30	0.86 ± 0.03	0.86 ± 0.03	0.59	0.60
mood-sad	10	0.89 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.03	0.65	0.65
mood-party	20	0.92 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.02	0.73	0.74
danceability	5	0.96 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.64	0.65
voice/instrumental	5	0.99 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01	0.80	0.79
gender	15	0.60 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.01	0.77	0.79
timbre	15	0.91 ± 0.01	0.88 ± 0.02	0.61	0.62
tonal/atonal	5	0.88 ± 0.18	0.79 ± 0.05	0.62	0.59

Table 18: Semantic-aware smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

by label smoothing. Label distribution learning has shown to be even more effective while being all the more dependent on each dataset's topological structure. We showed that incorporating this structural information consistently enhances the output label distributions, with regards to human perception. Estimating label distributions also acts as a label augmentation method, which provides more diverse "profiles" of training data points. Eventually, label distribution learning can give an implicit control over the way a model learns, while improving its generalization capacity even in limited data scenarios.

Meanwhile, automatically adapting the label distribution of each data point can be also interpreted as a very sensitive form of outliers detection. In both cases, the idea is to "filter out" a given dataset by tackling possible label incoherence. Through this angle, it is clear now that the data representation used throughout this process should try to correspond to interpretable attributes as much as possible. Varying the audio descriptors employed (timbral, rhythmical ...) and exploring new transformations could further improve the LDL approaches described in this work. For example, it is proposed in [106] to use a supervised Non-Negative Matrix factorisation of Constant Q-transform coefficients for sound classification. Such

Dataset	k_s	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	5	0.48 ± 0.27	0.46 ± 0.01	0.40	0.42
genre-gtzan	10	0.80 ± 0.23	0.80 ± 0.02	0.43	0.44
genre-rosamerica	5	0.81 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.02	0.46	0.59
mood-acoustic	15	0.94 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.04	0.70	0.72
mood-electronic	15	0.88 ± 0.39	0.84 ± 0.04	0.75	0.75
mood-aggressive	5	0.96 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.04	0.70	0.73
mood-relaxed	15	0.89 ± 0.30	0.90 ± 0.03	0.67	0.69
mood-happy	30	0.79 ± 0.05	0.83 ± 0.03	0.57	0.59
mood-sad	10	0.87 ± 0.22	0.87 ± 0.03	0.62	0.63
mood-party	10	0.91 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	0.72	0.73
danceability	20	0.93 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.04	0.69	0.69
voice/instrumental	15	0.93 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.03	0.77	0.78
gender	5	0.58 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.01	0.74	0.77
timbre	15	0.84 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.01	0.54	0.60
tonal/atonal	100	0.95 ± 0.03	0.79 ± 0.06	0.58	0.51

Table 19: Semantic-aware smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.

data transformations have the advantage of yielding more easily interpretable representations, on top of which could be estimated a distance function that would better fit each dataset. Finally, we believe that the distribution learning paradigm carries a lot more potential in ambiguous classification settings as the amount of training data increases. Estimating label distributions seems to be a more subtle and complex task than classification with hard labels. A larger training dataset can therefore improve the approximation of the actual label distributions by confronting the model to more and varied examples. Finally, more data also offers the possibility of employing deep learning-based approaches such as contrastive learning [107] where the data transformation space would contain more complex non-linear functions and can also be guided with data augmentation strategies preserving classes integrity.

5.2 Loss Functions

Our previous experiments on label smoothing have shown that this approach suffers from a high variability, largely due to a significant dependency between each classi-

fication task’s complexity and ambiguity. Moreover, these methods tend to increase possible bias induced by each dataset, which in the case of small-sized datasets, can be detrimental. The motivation of this section is to address the limitations encountered by label smoothing. To this end, we propose to keep each dataset intact and instead focus on ways to make each model and their training process more robust to problematic training instances. Previously in this report, we have highlighted how intervening on the loss values calculations can help make a given model more robust to label noise. In this chapter, we propose to experiment with different noise-robust loss functions and measure their impact on the generalization capacity of the MusiCNN and VGG models. More precisely, we choose to follow the different approaches adopted in [46] for acoustic event classification, which is to some extent, related to the classification tasks we are addressing in this work.

5.2.1 Bootstrapping

Method

Originally introduced in [61], the Bootstrapping method aims at augmenting the prediction objective with a degree of consistency. In this context, the idea of prediction consistency refers to the similarity of predictions formulated by the model throughout training, given similar inputs. One main advantage of this approach is that it does not require an explicit modelling of the label noise distribution, which greatly facilitates its use on noisy datasets where the amount of corrupted labels is unknown beforehand. The main idea of the Bootstrapping strategy is to dynamically update the targets of the prediction objective based on the current state of the model. To do so, the initial objective function is linearly combined with the current prediction made by the model during training. Intuitively, this can be motivated by the fact that the learner’s predictions get more and more reliable throughout training. Therefore, if a label is incorrect, it will eventually be highly inconsistent with other stimuli predicted to have the same label by the model. If we consider cross-entropy as the initial loss function, “soft” bootstrapping uses predicted class

probabilities \hat{y}_k directly to generate regression targets for each batch as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{soft} = - \sum_{k=1}^L [\beta y_k + (1 - \beta) \hat{y}_k] \log(\hat{y}_k), \beta \in [0, 1] \quad (5.8)$$

where y_k denote the true label of the k th example, and \hat{y}_k its respective prediction made by the model. As described in [61], it has been shown that employing a Bootstrapping approach pushes the model to formulate label predictions with a higher confidence than traditional approaches. Therefore, the resulting model tends to be more coherent and less impacted by mislabelled data points. Depending on the classification task, the best generalization boost was obtained either for $\beta = 0.5$ or $\beta = 0.7$.

Results

Dataset	β	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.5	0.61 \pm 0.02	0.60 \pm 0.02	0.42	0.44
genre-gtzan	0.5	0.88 \pm 0.01	0.88 \pm 0.02	0.46	0.46
genre-rosamerica	0.7	0.95 \pm 0.01	0.95 \pm 0.02	0.51	0.52
mood-acoustic	0.5	0.95 \pm 0.02	0.95 \pm 0.02	0.68	0.70
mood-electronic	0.7	0.93 \pm 0.03	0.93 \pm 0.02	0.72	0.73
mood-aggressive	0.7	0.97 \pm 0.02	0.98 \pm 0.01	0.67	0.66
mood-relaxed	0.7	0.89 \pm 0.03	0.88 \pm 0.03	0.64	0.69
mood-happy	0.5	0.86 \pm 0.03	0.87 \pm 0.02	0.59	0.61
mood-sad	0.5	0.89 \pm 0.04	0.89 \pm 0.04	0.65	0.65
mood-party	0.7	0.92 \pm 0.03	0.93 \pm 0.03	0.73	0.73
danceability	0.5	0.96 \pm 0.02	0.95 \pm 0.02	0.64	0.64
voice/instrumental	0.5	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.98 \pm 0.01	0.80	0.79
gender	0.5	0.60 \pm 0.02	0.62 \pm 0.01	0.77	0.79
timbre	0.5	0.91 \pm 0.01	0.91 \pm 0.01	0.61	0.61
tonal/atonal	0.7	0.88 \pm 0.18	0.88 \pm 0.02	0.62	0.63

Table 20: Bootstrapping loss on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

Despite improving the generalization performance on a few classification tasks, the efficiency of the bootstrapping approach seems to be limited. Even though taking the model’s predictions into account can improve consistency throughout training, considering these predictions too early during the optimization process can hamper

Dataset	β	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.7	0.48 ± 0.27	0.48 ± 0.01	0.40	0.40
genre-gtzan	0.5	0.80 ± 0.23	0.81 ± 0.03	0.43	0.41
genre-rosamerica	0.7	0.81 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.01	0.46	0.60
mood-acoustic	0.5	0.94 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.02	0.70	0.70
mood-electronic	0.5	0.88 ± 0.39	0.87 ± 0.03	0.75	0.74
mood-aggressive	0.7	0.96 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.01	0.70	0.69
mood-relaxed	0.7	0.89 ± 0.30	0.87 ± 0.03	0.67	0.65
mood-happy	0.7	0.79 ± 0.05	0.79 ± 0.03	0.57	0.55
mood-sad	0.5	0.87 ± 0.22	0.90 ± 0.02	0.62	0.63
mood-party	0.7	0.91 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	0.72	0.73
danceability	0.5	0.93 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.03	0.69	0.69
voice/instrumental	0.5	0.93 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.77	0.77
gender	0.7	0.58 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.02	0.74	0.73
timbre	0.7	0.84 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.02	0.54	0.57
tonal/atonal	0.7	0.95 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.02	0.58	0.58

Table 21: Bootstrapping loss on the VGG transfer learning model.

the final model’s performance. Despite the fact that both pre-trained models tend to converge relatively fast, their predictions made during the first few iterations are not reliable enough. Therefore, using a constant value for β might negatively affect the early parameters update. To address this issue, it could be possible to design a schedule followed by β to take very small values during a first training stage, and then start increasing as the model begins to learn more specific patterns.

5.2.2 Generalized Cross-Entropy

Method

The Generalized Cross-Entropy (GCE) can be viewed as a generalization of both the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Cross-Entropy (CE). More precisely, it is argued in [58] that CE implicitly gives more weight to incorrect predictions, which positively affects the training convergence for classification tasks but is likely to overfit on potential label noise. On the contrary, due to its symmetry, the MAE loss tends to treat all examples equally regardless of the model’s predictions. However, this can lead to a lower convergence pace. Therefore, GCE aims at benefiting both from the

noise-robustness of MAE and the way CE emphasizes on difficult examples during training. Given a batch of samples of size K , the GCE can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_q = \frac{1 - (\sum_{k=1}^K y_k \hat{y}_k)^q}{q}, q \in [0, 1] \quad (5.9)$$

Here, the parameter q acts as a balance coefficient between MAE and CE. Authors show in [58] that \mathcal{L}_q is equivalent to CE when $q \rightarrow 0$ and corresponds to MAE when $q = 1$. Moreover, the authors also illustrate the influence of the parameter q throughout different experiments, and draw the conclusion that for a label noise rate $\eta < 0.5$, a value of $q = 0.7$ gives a satisfying trade-off between a fast convergence and a reduced overfitting on examples with noisy labels. In our experiments, we used $q = 0.5$ and $q = 0.7$ and reported the best results obtained in Tables 22 and 23.

Results

Dataset	q	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.5	0.61 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.03	0.42	0.44
genre-gtzan	0.5	0.88 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.02	0.46	0.44
genre-rosamerica	0.7	0.95 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.01	0.51	0.51
mood-acoustic	0.5	0.95 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.68	0.68
mood-electronic	0.7	0.93 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.03	0.72	0.73
mood-aggressive	0.5	0.97 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.02	0.67	0.69
mood-relaxed	0.5	0.89 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.02	0.64	0.69
mood-happy	0.5	0.86 ± 0.03	0.86 ± 0.03	0.59	0.59
mood-sad	0.7	0.89 ± 0.04	0.89 ± 0.02	0.65	0.64
mood-party	0.5	0.92 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.03	0.73	0.74
danceability	0.7	0.96 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.03	0.64	0.67
voice/instrumental	0.7	0.99 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	0.80	0.79
gender	0.5	0.60 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.02	0.77	0.78
timbre	0.5	0.91 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.01	0.61	0.61
tonal/atonal	0.5	0.88 ± 0.18	0.89 ± 0.03	0.62	0.63

Table 22: Generalized Cross-Entropy loss on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

Experimental results summarized in Tables 22 and 23 show that the GCE loss can improve label noise robustness in some particular cases. For both architectures, up

Dataset	q	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.5	0.48 ± 0.27	0.47 ± 0.01	0.40	0.40
genre-gtzan	0.5	0.80 ± 0.23	0.81 ± 0.02	0.43	0.43
genre-rosamerica	0.5	0.81 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.03	0.46	0.47
mood-acoustic	0.7	0.94 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02	0.70	0.71
mood-electronic	0.7	0.88 ± 0.39	0.89 ± 0.06	0.75	0.76
mood-aggressive	0.5	0.96 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.01	0.70	0.68
mood-relaxed	0.7	0.89 ± 0.30	0.89 ± 0.02	0.67	0.68
mood-happy	0.5	0.79 ± 0.05	0.84 ± 0.01	0.57	0.58
mood-sad	0.5	0.87 ± 0.22	0.91 ± 0.03	0.62	0.62
mood-party	0.7	0.91 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	0.72	0.73
danceability	0.7	0.93 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.02	0.69	0.68
voice/instrumental	0.5	0.93 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.02	0.77	0.77
gender	0.7	0.58 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.01	0.74	0.76
timbre	0.5	0.84 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.02	0.54	0.58
tonal/atonal	0.5	0.95 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.01	0.58	0.58

Table 23: Generalized Cross-Entropy loss on the VGG transfer learning model.

to 8 classification tasks have been improved over the baseline. Without any clear pattern emerging from these results, it is worth noting that GCE has no positive impact on the two most ambiguous classification tasks: happy and sad. Despite relying on the MAE's noise robustness properties, the GCE loss does not build an explicit modelling of ambiguity but rather ends up considering very "ambiguous" data points as mislabelled, and improve the model's robustness against these. In other words, GCE pushes the model to learn the most common patterns present in each class, while simply limiting the influence of difficult examples. However, we believe that this type of noise robust loss function could yield better improvements as the amount of training data increases. Larger datasets will enhance the focus made by the model on important patterns from the data, which will indirectly improve the robustness against either label noise or too specific attributes of the training set.

5.2.3 Outlier-Aware Cross-Entropy

Method

The work carried out in [108] shows that neural networks tend to first learn easy and regular patterns before memorizing noise present in the data. Motivated by these results, authors in [46] propose a two-step training process in order to reduce the impact of label noise at the latter stage of the learning process. They first propose to use a noise-robust loss function up to a given number of epochs n_1 . Then, as the model is assumed to be reliable enough regarding its predictions, they discard large loss instances at every iteration. More precisely, for a given mini-batch of data, they mask the loss value of any data point that is bigger than $m + l \times s$ where m and s are the median and standard deviation calculated over the mini-batch loss values respectively and l a hyper-parameter to be fixed. It is important to note that the transfer-learning based models considered in this work tend to converge fast, which implies low values for the parameter n_1 . We experiment with $n_1 = 5$ for Mood and Miscellaneous classification tasks and $n_1 = 10$ for Genre classification. Each model is first trained using the GCE loss up to n_1 epochs, and then using the truncated loss proposed here. In all cases, we use $l = 2$ and the model is trained for a total number of 150 epochs.

Results

The two-stage training strategy generally gives sparse improvements over the baseline models trained with cross-entropy. Even though it limits the learning of patterns proper to the training data, this strategy does not address the notion of ambiguity among classes. Therefore, even early updates are pushed towards hard labels, which does not reflect the classification task as much as label smoothing. However in some cases, such as Genre or Miscellaneous classification tasks, it appears as an efficient way to cope with overfitting. Since both pre-trained models converge relatively fast, this training strategy could surely yield different results on models trained from scratch. In that scenario, the value of n_1 would impact how specific the learning process is carried out. Similarly, the parameter l could be re-adjusted throughout

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.61 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.03	0.42	0.43
genre-gtzan	0.88 ± 0.01	0.87 ± 0.03	0.46	0.45
genre-rosamerica	0.95 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.02	0.51	0.54
mood-acoustic	0.95 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.68	0.69
mood-electronic	0.93 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.02	0.72	0.71
mood-aggressive	0.97 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.02	0.67	0.64
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.03	0.64	0.68
mood-happy	0.86 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.01	0.59	0.57
mood-sad	0.89 ± 0.04	0.88 ± 0.02	0.65	0.63
mood-party	0.92 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.03	0.73	0.72
danceability	0.96 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.02	0.64	0.65
voice/instrumental	0.99 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	0.80	0.81
gender	0.60 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.02	0.77	0.79
timbre	0.91 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.02	0.61	0.62
tonal/atonal	0.88 ± 0.18	0.87 ± 0.01	0.62	0.60

Table 24: Outlier-aware Cross-Entropy loss on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

training in order to dynamically filter out unnecessary information.

5.2.4 Conclusion

Adjusting the loss calculation to datasets with unknown noise ratios is still an active area of research. We have seen in this section that carefully designing noise-robust loss functions can, in some cases, improve training and eventually extend generalization capacities. Unlike label smoothing, robust loss functions do not directly aim at addressing label ambiguity. However, they can have a similar effect since very ambiguous training data points might, in some way, be regarded as noisy instances. The three loss functions explored in this work individually rely on different principles. The bootstrapping method and the outlier-aware loss function make use of the notions of consistency and are heavily based on the model’s predictions confidence. The generalized cross-entropy combines characteristics of symmetric losses with the fast convergence of cross-entropy. It is important to note that, once again, each loss function’s efficiency strongly depends on the task addressed. Further work could be needed in order to build dynamic loss functions, able to adapt to any classification

Dataset	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
	Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
genre-dortmund	0.48 ± 0.27	0.47 ± 0.01	0.40	0.40
genre-gtzan	0.80 ± 0.23	0.81 ± 0.01	0.43	0.44
genre-rosamerica	0.81 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.01	0.46	0.60
mood-acoustic	0.94 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02	0.70	0.71
mood-electronic	0.88 ± 0.39	0.88 ± 0.02	0.75	0.74
mood-aggressive	0.96 ± 0.11	0.95 ± 0.03	0.70	0.72
mood-relaxed	0.89 ± 0.30	0.89 ± 0.03	0.67	0.66
mood-happy	0.79 ± 0.05	0.81 ± 0.02	0.57	0.57
mood-sad	0.87 ± 0.22	0.91 ± 0.02	0.62	0.64
mood-party	0.91 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	0.72	0.72
danceability	0.93 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.02	0.69	0.69
voice/instrumental	0.93 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.77	0.77
gender	0.58 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.03	0.74	0.77
timbre	0.84 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.02	0.54	0.57
tonal/atonal	0.95 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.02	0.58	0.57

Table 25: Outlier-aware Cross-Entropy loss on the VGG transfer learning model.

task. As an example, Gao et al. in [109] propose a meta learning-based method to automatically construct white-box classification loss functions that are robust to label noise in the training data. Additionally, the learned loss functions could also be explicitly constrained such that they take the amount of ambiguity of each specific task into consideration. Such amount of ambiguity could be estimated using topological analysis tools of the dataset, and how well separated the different classes are.

Chapter 6

Knowledge Transfer

In this work, several strategies have been listed in order to address the issue of generalization of different classification models. In this chapter, we propose to explore how a given classification task can be informed by other ones. The experimental setting of this work consists of 15 classification tasks provided with their own set of songs and labels. The question that arises is the following: *Can a classification task benefit from information extracted from one or other classification tasks?* We propose one main axis of response to this question, relying on knowledge transfer among tasks. It has been noted that each dataset has a very small size compared to the amount of data deep learning models usually need to perform efficiently. We can assume that each dataset might carry relevant information for other classification tasks. Similarly, it is also possible to share information among different classification tasks directly throughout training. As previously described in this report, it is sometimes possible for some tasks to leverage and share the same type of information from the data, which pushes their corresponding models to build relatively similar representations. The MTL paradigm has the potential to alleviate possible relationships among tasks, enhance the overall learning process and improve the generalization capacity of the resulting model. Therefore, we finally propose to experiment with a simple MTL approach that will jointly learn pairs of classification tasks.

6.1 Multi-Task Learning

The current setting in which this work fits led us to wonder whether a classification task A could inform a classification task B with different categories. Intuitively speaking, the nature of the classification tasks considered in this work tend to argue in favor of this assumption. For example, determining that a song is aggressive indirectly informs about whether it is relaxing. From this idea of inter-dependency among tasks, it is possible to infer which pairs of tasks could benefit from being learned jointly or not. More precisely, two tasks could potentially benefit from each other in the two following cases:

- Information leveraged: the two tasks tend to look for the same types of patterns in the data. For example, we can assume that the happy and party tasks would learn towards the same direction as they are semantically close.
- Class opposition: some pairs of tasks might indirectly inform each other due to their classes opposition. For example, if two tasks are semantically conflicting (relaxed and aggressive, happy and sad ...), then they almost correspond to each other's contrary and might result in the same type of decision function where the positive case for a task is the negative one for the other.

In order to verify if different classification tasks can be efficiently learned jointly, and whether or not the improvements follow an intuitive task grouping, we propose to learn various pairs of tasks simultaneously. To guarantee tasks compatibility, we only applied the MTL training method to Mood classification tasks, as we know for sure that each song from any of these datasets has to fall within a category of any other dataset. Extending this approach to Genre and Miscellaneous categories would require a more thorough data selection process. For example, songs without any vocals could not be used to improve the Gender task. The same problem arises for Genre classification where some audio extracts from a given dataset might not fall within the categories of another one. It is also preferable to avoid any additional data labelling and use the different datasets as they are. As a consequence, we employ

the alternating training strategy briefly described earlier in this report. Finally, we also show that throughout training, it is possible to extend the MTL approach by inferring pseudo-labels at each iteration. The resulting model is then trained on slightly larger datasets for both classification problems it is designed to solve.

6.1.1 Disjoint Multi-Task Learning

Introduced in [77], the disjoint MTL approach addresses disjoint datasets situations by essentially using a shared network, acting as a feature extractor, on top of which are added classification (or regression) heads, each individually designed to perform a specific task. Unlike traditional MTL approaches, MTL with disjoint datasets has to our knowledge, never been applied to audio related classification tasks. In our case, we use the pre-trained VGG and MusiCNN models as feature extractors. Then, a shared hidden layer of size 100 and ReLU activations is added, followed by two classification heads (softmax activations). The training process is formalized as follows: Let $\mathcal{D}_A = \{\mathbf{x}_1^a, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n_a}^a\}$ be the dataset associated with a task A , and $\mathcal{D}_B = \{\mathbf{x}_1^b, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{n_b}^b\}$ with a different task B , where n_a and n_b are the number of training instances for \mathcal{D}_A and \mathcal{D}_B respectively. In epoch $t - 1$, the network will be trained with points from \mathcal{D}_A and the shared parameters Θ_s will be optimized according to the predictions made by the head A given the ground-truth label vectors \mathbf{y}_i^a . Similarly at epoch t , the network is trained on dataset \mathcal{D}_B and its parameters are optimized accordingly. This procedure is then repeated until reaching the total number of training iterations required. As shown in Figure 9, each iteration will solely focus on one single output of the model, where there exist available ground-truth vectors. The overall optimization process ends up being bi-directional, as it not only looks for a representation yielding good performance for one task, but for two different ones simultaneously. In this training setting, the best version of the model for each task is saved and further used for testing. For both tasks, we used a constant learning rate $\alpha = 0.001$ and a categorical cross-entropy loss. We report the best results obtained per classification task and the auxiliary task learned simultaneously.

Figure 9: Alternate MTL training with two tasks.

6.1.2 Results

Main Task	Aux. Task	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
mood-acoustic	mood-happy	0.95 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.68	0.69
mood-electronic	mood-acoustic	0.93 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.02	0.72	0.76
mood-aggressive	mood-happy	0.97 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.67	0.68
mood-relaxed	mood-acoustic	0.89 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.01	0.64	0.69
mood-happy	mood-acoustic	0.86 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.02	0.59	0.62
mood-sad	mood-happy	0.89 ± 0.04	0.87 ± 0.03	0.65	0.65
mood-party	mood-relaxed	0.92 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.03	0.73	0.74

Table 26: Multi-Task results on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.

Before delving into the generalization performance of the two MTL models, we detail a few characteristics about the learning phase and how it differs from task-specific models'. Although much higher training losses were observed with the MTL approach than for original models, it seems that the multi-task method extracts deeper information from the data. Due to the bi-directionality of the optimization process, the representation learned by the common last layer of the network complies with specificities of both classification tasks. However, we also noticed a few elements likely to be detrimental to learning. First, each task seems to have its own

Main Task	Aux. Task	5-fold CV		Evaluation	
		Baseline	Proposed	Baseline	Proposed
mood-acoustic	mood-relaxed	0.94 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.04	0.70	0.71
mood-electronic	mood-party	0.88 ± 0.39	0.86 ± 0.07	0.75	0.74
mood-aggressive	mood-sad	0.96 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.03	0.70	0.73
mood-relaxed	mood-sad	0.89 ± 0.30	0.90 ± 0.03	0.67	0.69
mood-happy	mood-party	0.79 ± 0.05	0.80 ± 0.04	0.57	0.59
mood-sad	mood-relaxed	0.87 ± 0.22	0.90 ± 0.03	0.62	0.63
mood-party	mood-happy	0.91 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.1	0.72	0.72

Table 27: Multi-Task results on the VGG transfer learning model.

convergence pace, which can cause an imbalanced training when one task is "prioritized" over the second. As for the best and worst task combinations, results reported in Table 26 and Table 27 show that they do not always follow an intuitive grouping. For example, results of the pair "aggressive" & "sad" in Table 27 surprisingly show an generalization improvement on the aggressive classification task. However, most of the other pairs such as "electronic" & "party" or "happy" & "sad" tend to be more consistent with the assumptions made above (type of information and class opposition). Similarly, less counter-intuitive pairs of tasks such as "electronic" & "sad" yielded very poor results. We can therefore assume that there exist a link between the semantic proximity among labels and how efficient it is to learn their associated classification tasks jointly. Throughout different experiments, we also found that the order in which tasks are shown to the model seems to have little to no impact on the joint-training outcome. Considering the simplicity of the joint-training strategy, the positive impact that multi-task approaches might have on generalization performance could further be improved. First, the difference in convergence speed among tasks could be addressed by tuning learning rates accordingly. This would potentially balance gradient updates and lead the overall optimization process to a better local minimum. There also exist different methods operating on the gradient calculation. For example, the Gradient Surgery Method proposed by Yu et al. in [110] aims at limiting interference between task gradients and improves training efficiency by gradient projections. Second, training all possible pairs of tasks is a tedious and time-consuming procedure, which could be avoided leveraging a-priori knowledge about relationships among classification tasks.

6.1.3 Two-Step Training

The alternating training strategy previously introduced show that the MTL paradigm can be a convenient way of dealing with relatively close classification tasks. Here, we propose a possible extension of this training method that could easily be implemented as future improvements. One can notice that throughout training, each iteration solely focuses on the error committed by the model for one task. As seen in Section 6.1.1 where the tasks addressed have distinct convergence paces, we saw that this training method can lead to *catastrophic forgetting*, which means that the model fails to learn tasks in a sequential manner. If we suppose that dataset A is used during the current epoch, then the training process is only supervised by the ground-truth labels of A , while no update is made according to the error made by the classification head designed for task B . To preserve knowledge acquired throughout training, Learning without Forgetting (LwF) is originally introduced in [111]. Further extended in [78], the principle of this method consists in supervising the classification head deprived of ground-truth by formulating pseudo-labels from the predictions outputted. More precisely, pseudo-labels are built as follows: if we assume that dataset A is used at epoch $t - 1$, then the pseudo label vector $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i^B$ for the classification head B is obtained from its predictions $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_i^B$ by simply setting the highest component to 1 and all the others to 0. The final loss function optimized at iteration $t - 1$ will be calculated as follows:

$$\min_{\theta^s} \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} [\beta \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}_i^A, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_i^A) + (1 - \beta) \mathcal{L}(\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_i^B, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_i^B)], \beta \in [0, 1] \quad (6.1)$$

where θ^s are the shared parameters of the network and n_a is the number of training examples in dataset A . We also add the constraint that pseudo labels will only be calculated from weak predictions having a value higher than a certain confidence threshold $\alpha = 0.7$. As loss functions \mathcal{L} , we use the CCE. Additionally, we apply a uniform smoothing with $\alpha = 0.1$ on the loss term that builds pseudo-labels, which further reduces the impact of wrongly inferred targets. Finally, we divide the training process into two steps, in the same way as in Paragraph 5.2.3. The underlying

assumption is that the model becomes more confident as training progresses, which improves the exactness of future pseudo-labels. For up to n_1 epochs, the MTL model is only trained on its task-specific supervised losses. Then, the model is optimized using the loss function from Equation 6.1.

6.2 Further Transfer

The architecture proposed in Section 6.1, despite its simplicity, already shows the potential of MTL approaches in situations where related classification tasks are addressed. It is clear that knowledge is shared across tasks through the internal representation learned by the model due to the bi-directionality of the optimization process. However, it is also possible to introduce information from auxiliary tasks through different mediums. In this section, we suggest further means of enabling knowledge sharing among classification tasks: data sharing, modelling task similarities and employing a meta-objective across learning experiences.

6.2.1 Semi-Supervised Learning

Motivated by our experiments in Section 6.1.3 and the small size of the training datasets used in this work, we propose here to describe how semi-supervised learning could potentially address the lack of data by making use of auxiliary datasets to generalize better at a given task. Semi-supervised learning is an approach that combines a small amount of labeled data with a large amount of unlabeled data during training [112]. To do so, some of the most direct semi-supervised methods usually require propagating labels from labelled to unlabelled data points. Several methods for label propagation have been investigated [112], with a majority of them relying on the three assumptions listed in Section 5.1.2. Semi-supervised learning has the ability to considerably improve performance over fully-supervised approaches, as the resulting model is trained on much larger datasets and thus, less subject to dataset bias. In the context of audio classification, semi-supervised learning has notably improved the performance of numerous algorithms, from instrument recognition [113], sound event [114] or music genre classification [115] and chord estimation [116]. In

the context of this work, it is important to first notice that a given song s necessarily belongs to one class in each classification problem addressed (except genres). Therefore, it seems perceptually relevant to propagate labels from a source dataset A to a target dataset B , as all songs in B fall within one of the classes of A . Second, some label propagation algorithms enable to weight instances with unreliable soft labels, so that their possibly negative influence on the overall training process is limited. All in all, the supervised-learning paradigm seems to be a promising research direction in the field of music classification especially due to large quantities of non-annotated music data available online for example. Eventually, increasing data quantity leads to a more diverse training dataset that enables classifiers to build more general representations and reduce domain-shift related issues.

6.2.2 Task Similarities

As witnessed from the results reported in Sections 6.1 and 6.1.3, the efficiency of the MTL approach strongly depends on the pair of tasks being learned. We can hypothesize about a need for statistical relationships among tasks so that the joint learning strategy ends up being beneficial for both of them. Therefore, one can ask the following question: *Is it possible to efficiently calculate a predictive measure of positive or negative transfer for a given pair of tasks ?* Such a predictive transfer measure could help in deciding which pairs of tasks are more likely to yield good performance without having to experimentally search for those. Similar questions have already been studied in the field of transfer learning [117]. For example, Yang et al. in [118] propose a method to quantify the relatedness between source and target tasks, and choose the amount of information to be shared accordingly among these tasks. Analogous methods exist for domain similarity estimation [119] where it is possible to predict the quality of transfer from a source to a target task. For example, to measure how much two domains differ, it is possible to compare characteristics of their original feature space. In case of *distant transfer*, data selection methods can be employed. Tan et al. in [120] propose an instance selection mechanism that identifies relevant source data to better improve the target task. Such methods could be further extended to the MTL setting such as in [121] or [122], where it

could also be possible to infer hierarchies among two tasks A and B such as $A \subseteq B$, $A \supseteq B$ or $A \approx B$. Finally, gaining insight on tasks' mutual relationships could also unveil new knowledge about music perception in general, and how very high level musical notions such as genre or mood are related to each other from an algorithmic perspective.

6.2.3 Meta-Learning

The idea of knowledge transfer among tasks is mainly motivated by the human perception of music. When listening to music, we can assume that humans are able to naturally accommodate to different tasks such as recognizing the genre, following the tempo or extracting the melody of a song. More generally, they seem to be able to learn new skills and formulate abstract representations of musical concepts very fast, even without any formal musical training. In this context, it is probable that while learning, humans acquire a deeper understanding about music that they reuse when confronted to new tasks. In other words, humans make use of prior learning experiences to apprehend new and unknown tasks. In order to algorithmically translate this paradigm, it is necessary to not only optimize a classifier on a particular task, but on a series of tasks it has been exposed to. The Meta-Learning paradigm, also known as "learning to learn", aims at addressing traditional machine learning limitations such as the lack of data or computational deficiency, by improving the learning algorithm itself. Such improvements involve information acquired during previous learning episodes and enable the model to generalize well on new tasks that have never been encountered during training time [123]. This approach has recently been gaining a lot of popularity, and is used to tackle various applications of machine learning. One of the few experiments that applied meta-learning to musical tasks is described in [124]. A set of ten tasks from the field of MIR is selected and arbitrarily separated into two subsets to train and test the meta-learning algorithm. At test time, the proposed method is compared to task-specific models that are trained from scratch. The author reports mixed results. For the majority of the selected tasks, this approach does not significantly perform better than models trained from scratch. However, despite the poor performance of the proposed method, this work

does highlight the promising capacity of meta-learning algorithms to be applied to music related tasks. In our context, the meta-learning paradigm could serve as an alternative to transfer learning to pre-train each model. This way, it would be possible to build one unique "super learner" capable of adapting itself to each single classification task by benefiting from a parameters initialization that is more representative of the general problem of music classification. Such initialization could then be used by the model as a form of prior knowledge when confronted to a new task as in [125]. Once again, such prior could be constrained to take each dataset's topological structure into account and result in a more flexible pre-training stage for the model.

6.3 Conclusion

Music classification remains a challenging problem in MIR as most of the classes tend to be high-level musical attributes such as genres or moods. Unlike other data types, music has a highly complex and relational structure that makes classification even more difficult. In this section, we made an attempt to leverage the overall structure of both music, and the classification tasks addressed in this project. With a basic Multi-Task approach, we highlighted the potential of this paradigm. The simple MTL architecture we experimented with tends to perform as well as baseline models, while learning two tasks jointly. From these results, it is possible to conclude that some classification tasks might benefit from a joint-learning strategy if paired up with one that is similar enough. Additionally, if a single model is able to find convenient representations for two tasks at the same time, we can also assume that task-specific models are likely to be too complex, which makes them prone to overfitting. The main advantage of the knowledge transfer approach is that it can also greatly benefit from other music-related disciplines such as musicology, cognitive sciences or music perception theory [126], [127]. Getting insight on how humans perceive music, learn and carry out music-related tasks can potentially help guiding new research directions related to knowledge transfer among MIR tasks.

Chapter 7

Discussion

The goal of this work was to give guidelines and axes of research in order to improve the generalization of deep learning music classifiers. We proposed improvements at three different levels of the training process. We evaluated each method on two state-of-the-art CNN architectures for music classification: MusiCNN and VGG. Throughout this chapter, we give an overview of each approach and list the best results obtained per classification task. We then summarize the different contributions of this work and suggest further research directions to be followed.

7.1 Overall Evaluation

The different methods experimented in this work have led to varying improvements over the baseline performance of both the MusiCNN and VGG pre-trained models. In order to have a more general view of the generalization boost achieved, we propose to list by task and architecture the highest classification scores obtained on the MTG-Jamendo dataset and the corresponding methods used.

Results from Table 28 clearly show that the generalization performance of both architectures on the majority of the datasets has increased. Note that in case of various methods yielding the same generalization improvements, we arbitrarily selected one of them to appear. Therefore, Table 28 should not be considered as a comparison

Dataset	Model					
	MusiCNN			VGG		
	Baseline	Proposed	Method	Baseline	Proposed	Method
genre-dortmund	0.42	0.44	DA	0.40	0.45	S_{weighted}
genre-gtzan	0.46	0.46	DA	0.43	0.44	S_{semantic}
genre-rosamerica	0.51	0.54	S_{uniform}	0.46	0.63	S_{weighted}
mood-acoustic	0.68	0.71	S_{semantic}	0.70	0.72	S_{semantic}
mood-electronic	0.72	0.77	S_{semantic}	0.75	0.76	S_{uniform}
mood-aggressive	0.67	0.69	DA	0.70	0.73	MTL
mood-relaxed	0.64	0.69	DA	0.67	0.69	MTL
mood-happy	0.59	0.62	MTL	0.57	0.61	DA
mood-sad	0.65	0.65	S_{uniform}	0.62	0.64	OCE
mood-party	0.73	0.74	S_{semantic}	0.72	0.73	S_{semantic}
danceability	0.64	0.67	GCE	0.69	0.69	S_{uniform}
voice/instrumental	0.80	0.81	OCE	0.77	0.78	S_{semantic}
gender	0.77	0.79	S_{uniform}	0.74	0.77	S_{semantic}
timbre	0.61	0.63	DA	0.54	0.61	S_{local}
tonal/atonal	0.62	0.66	S_{local}	0.58	0.59	DA

Table 28: Best evaluation results summary on MTG-Jamendo (DA=Data Augmentation, S_a =Label Smoothing of type a , B=Boostrapping, GCE=Generalized Cross Entropy, OCE=Outlier Cross Entropy, MTL=Multi-Task Learning).

among methods, but rather as an overall appreciation of progress made against the baseline results. It is important to notice the gap between the average accuracy boosts obtained by each model: $2.33 \pm 1.49\%$ for the MusiCNN and $3.57 \pm 4.10\%$ for the VGG one. Despite the fact that the methods proposed in this work are generally model-agnostic, the choice of architecture seems to influence the results obtained. Additionally, the two worst generalization scores obtained still remain equal to the baseline. It is worth noting the positive impact that label smoothing has over the different tasks and how the semantic-approach that we proposed usually outperforms any other smoothing strategy. The multi-task training strategy also brings competitive generalization improvements despite the exhaustive search for compatible pairs of tasks. All in all, results from Table 28 illustrate how promising the three research axes of this work are, and suggest further improvements with additional hyper-parameters search or approaches combinations.

Another aspect of the evaluation that we did not comment on is the eventual per-

formance gap in the 5-fold cross-validation setting that can arise in some cases. There does not seem to be any clear pattern linking that performance to the generalization ability of each model. However, we do note that in a majority of cases, 5-fold cross-validation results remain consistent between the baseline and the improvements proposed. Therefore we can assume that for similar training outcomes, a generalization improvement implies that the model learned more general features throughout training, without degrading its performance on that same training set.

7.2 Summary of Contributions

We propose now to qualitatively summarize the outcomes of this work. We list important notions that have been learned throughout each experiment and the efficiency of the proposed methods.

In Chapter 4, we showed the impact the quality and quantity of training data can have on the final generalization performance. We described the high complexity of automatically treating audio outliers, especially in the context of music classification. We also designed a simple augmentation policy directly applicable on mel-spectrograms that preserves labels' integrity. Within this augmentation chain, we showed that noise addition in the time domain can be safely approximated by a similar noise in the time-frequency domain. Overall, we highlighted the dependency of both outliers detection and audio augmentation methods to the classification tasks addressed. To tackle this, we finally provided guidelines and future research directions to improve augmentation methods' adaptation to specific datasets.

As our second main contribution, we showed in Chapter 5 that the problem of music classification can greatly benefit from ambiguity and label noise modelling. We first saw that approximating a continuous labels distribution instead of discrete targets helps encompassing the perceptual vagueness of some classification problems. We developed a label smoothing method that relies on a linear transformation (i.e metric learning) of the data guided by label information. We showed that learning this new metric simultaneously reduces dimensionality and spreads data points onto

a perceptually relevant space. When then applied a k-NN based smoothing on coordinates of that new space and showed that it performs notably better than when operating directly in the feature space. Our approach also tends to give more consistent improvements over the baseline in a limited data situation. We argue that the search of semantically relevant low dimensional spaces can greatly improve generalization results for label distribution learning. We gave further approaches relying on matrix factorization and deep learning to find such convenient spaces. Although not being as effective as label smoothing, we experimented with noise-robust loss functions and highlighted their potential benefits even in small datasets scenarios.

Finally in Chapter 6, we investigated how classification tasks can inform each other and leverage common information from data throughout training. We illustrated this assumption using a basic MTL approach that can be adapted to any model with an auxiliary dataset, which can be easily acquired in practice. We then proposed an extension the MTL method using pseudo-labels construction. We eventually gave further directions in order to quantify, evaluate and optimize the notion of knowledge transfer among tasks through different paradigms: semi-supervised learning, transfer-learning and meta-learning.

7.3 Future Work

Throughout this report, we have given different directions to further improve each method implemented. We propose here to list complementary ideas of future work on two different levels: general and practical. By general, we refer to improvements and axes of research in the broad line of music classification. By practical, we refer to the improvements of the two particular pre-trained models employed in this work.

The increasing amount of music data available comes with various drawbacks such as the lack of associated labels, or, their inaccuracy. As most deep learning-based music classifiers rely on supervised learning, there is a need to efficiently extract and reuse knowledge from limited quantities of sometimes, wrongly annotated data. As

an implicit form of label augmentation, label distribution learning has the potential to simultaneously deal with both label noise and small datasets. Moreover, training data is in practice subject to ambiguity, either due to the nature of the task or the subjectivity implied by different annotators. Further work is needed in order to better approximate a semantic space, where local smoothing methods would operate on task-related meaningful features. Additionally, the inherent complex structure of music naturally implies a deep relationship between different music classification tasks. As previously described, too few approaches have been proposed in order to more precisely characterize and optimize tasks relationships and their transfer. The same conclusion can arise in a broader perspective with different tasks of MIR that could possibly benefit each other if learned together.

In a more practical manner, this work proposed independent guidelines to improve the generalization capacity music classifiers. Throughout each experiment, only a handful of hyper-parameters have been set to satisfying values without any extensive search, which leaves room for potential progress. For example, the semantic smoothing method introduced would improve if the right trade-off between sensitivity and selectivity is determined at the metric-learning stage. Combining some of these methods together would also improve generalization. With a better optimized data augmentation policy and the proposed semantic smoothing method, it is possible to show the model more examples of the overall labels distribution and inflate the effect of label smoothing. Label distribution learning can also be combined with the proposed MTL training strategy, where one could apply stronger and more complex smoothing methods on the task that tends to converge the fastest, and therefore reduce the magnitude of the updates made in that direction. The same applies for noise robust loss functions that could prevent the MTL model to be subject to each dataset's noise, and therefore stabilize the optimization process. Since all the experiments were carried out on pre-trained models, performing the same tests on models trained from scratch would give further insight about each method's efficiency. Varying the number of frozen layers in pre-trained models could also emphasize the effect of each method, and potentially increase their efficiency. For example, the use of audio data augmentation or multi-task learning is likely change the way features

are extracted from the input, or how the internal representation embedded deeper into the network is built. To have a better understanding of the results obtained, it would also be interesting to look at inter-rater agreement measures for each classification task, and therefore know if our methods do deal with labels ambiguity and subjectivity. Finally, the pre-training stage on audio-tagging tasks of each architecture could be further studied in order to maximize the quality of transfer from music auto-tagging to music classification. Other pre-training strategies could also be imagined using for example encoder-decoder architectures or meta-objectives.

7.4 Conclusion

The task of automatically analyzing music requires complying with various constraints inherent to the nature of music: a complex relational structure, a high dimensionality, an important temporal dependency and more generally, a lack of very large annotated datasets. These elements make music classification a challenging and unresolved problem. Additionally, some classification tasks involve high-level music-concepts that are not always thoroughly formalized. Therefore, even carefully annotated datasets can carry important amounts of ambiguity or subjectivity in their label distribution. In this work, we proposed guidelines at three different levels of the training process of deep learning music classifiers aiming at improving their generalization performance to external audio collections. Results obtained show that each of these methods have a direct impact on generalization by reducing the variance of each model and suggest promising research directions to improve the task of automatic music classification. Moreover, the experimental setting in which these methods have been evaluated also prove that they can be effective in insufficient training data situations. More precisely, we showed that an optimized audio data augmentation policy, an explicit modelling of label noise and ambiguity with the use potential transfer of knowledge among tasks appear as efficient ways to cope with overfitting and enhance generalization capacities of deep learning music classifiers. From a more general perspective, the outcomes of this work on classification can also unveil new perspectives on other MIR tasks. Automatic musical structure

estimation, instrument recognition, music recommendation or transcription are all problems involving a classification step. As a consequence, some of the methods proposed in this work could potentially be employed for such tasks and ultimately improve their performance.

List of Figures

1	Relationship between the number of training examples and training and test error (left). Relationship between the number of parameters and training and test error (right). Adapted from [8].	4
2	mel-spectrogram Noise Distribution per song (Happy/not Happy dataset).	42
3	mel-spectrogram Noise Approximation per song (Happy/not Happy dataset).	42
4	2-D t-SNE projection of the GTZAN Dataset (Averaged MFCC features).	62
5	2-D t-SNE projection of the "Relaxed" Dataset (Averaged MFCC features).	62
6	Objectives of the LMNN algorithm, adapted from [104].	64
7	2-D t-SNE projection of the GTZAN Dataset (PCA & LMNN).	67
8	2-D t-SNE projection of the "Relaxed" Dataset (PCA & LMNN).	68
9	Alternate MTL training with two tasks.	82

List of Tables

1	MTG In-house music collections (ft.: full tracks, exc.: excerpts). Adapted from [23].	24
2	Experimental results of MP-Reject for the happy/not happy dataset.	34
3	Experimental results of MP-Reject for the relaxed/not relaxed dataset.	34
4	Experimental results of LOF for the happy/not happy dataset.	35
5	Experimental results of LOF for the relaxed/not relaxed dataset.	35
6	Experimental results of MP-Reject for the GTZAN dataset.	36
7	Experimental results of LOF for the GTZAN dataset.	36
8	Augmentation Policy, where N corresponds to the number of times each transformation is applied, and position refers to their overall position within the chaining strategy.	44
9	Data augmentation influence on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	45
10	Data augmentation influence on the VGG transfer learning model.	46
11	Uniform smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	50
12	Uniform smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.	51
13	Local smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	55
14	Local smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.	56
15	Weighted smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	59
16	Weighted smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.	60
17	Semantic-Aware smoothing hyperparameter values.	65
18	Semantic-aware smoothing on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	69
19	Semantic-aware smoothing on the VGG transfer learning model.	70
20	Bootstrapping loss on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	72
21	Bootstrapping loss on the VGG transfer learning model.	73

22	Generalized Cross-Entropy loss on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	74
23	Generalized Cross-Entropy loss on the VGG transfer learning model.	75
24	Outlier-aware Cross-Entropy loss on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	77
25	Outlier-aware Cross-Entropy loss on the VGG transfer learning model.	78
26	Multi-Task results on the MusiCNN transfer learning model.	82
27	Multi-Task results on the VGG transfer learning model.	83
28	Best evaluation results summary on MTG-Jamendo (DA=Data Augmentation, S_a =Label Smoothing of type a , B=Boostrapping, GCE=Generalized Cross Entropy, OCE=Outlier Cross Entropy, MTL=Multi-Task Learning).	90

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